

The Standard Model spacetime algebra and topology

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There is a scantily explored alternative to (i) gauge fibres “living” on spacetime and (ii) strings & branes, and (iii) cellular automata & spin network, causal nets, and other discretized models. This alternative seeks to find Lie algebra structure within local non-trivial spacetime topology (colloquially “wormhole topology” suitably generalized). This program is a variety of geometrodynamics, but differing in subtle ways from the older school program of Wheeler and Misner. Modern developments in quantum information technology (QIT) give theoreticians a few new tools to explore geometrodynamics without the overwhelming complications of algebraic topology and all that mind boggling depth of “abstract nonsense.” We review some basics for such a program and provide some questions worth exploring. We emphasize that a plausible path to a real geometry for the Standard Model could be found in the Clifford algebra Cl_8 or in a doubling of the spacetime algebra $Cl_{3,1}$, which in 4D spacetime context strongly implies Planck scale topology is non-trivial (as expected by most theorists working in *quantum gravity*). We use these results to motivate the idea that explicit complex structure: $Cl_8 \otimes Cl_{0,2}$, yielding Cl_8 , can be loosely interpreted as the algebraic shadow of 4-geon wormhole structure.

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I. INTRODUCTION

We begin with a very cursory survey of Clifford algebra approaches towards the Standard Model. This introductory section will be mainly philosophical and non-technical. The point is to motivate choices. As we will see, there are an embarrassment of options, all of which look promising but which each suffer some shortcomings. The young researcher could spend years studying all the different approaches, and so a conceptual overview might be helpful for choosing where to dive in, and that is the purpose of our introduction.

This paper is a *pre*-preprint, in that we have allowed ourselves some philosophical ramblings in order to help organize our thoughts, and because this is part of the (usually unpublished) scientific process we thought it

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could help inspire students. We imagine such inspiration could occur *particularly* when a student finds that they strongly object to something we claim. In that clash often comes the sparks which drive fruitful science.

I.A. Clifford algebra approaches

Several authors have sought the Standard Model (SM) of particle physics in various algebras [1–8]. Some relate the SM to Jordan algebras [9, 10]. Several of these efforts are loosely “united” by employing the Clifford algebra Cl_6 , or $Cl_{6,1}$ or Cl_7 . Two in particular that are promising have a potential natural chirality [5, 11].

We have previously taken to attempting to align with Gresnigt et al [12, 13], [11], Todorov [6] Lisi [8] and Lasenby [7] as the closest we have found to spacetime topology models. However, all three authors present quite different appearing approaches, making a synthesis somewhat of a struggle.

Although we do not have proof, it appears that the algebra $Cl_{1,6}$ is not big enough for three generations of fermions [1, 3]. What seems to occur is a complexification of $Cl_{3,1}$ to obtain one generation, then authors move to $Cl_{6,1}$ which has a natural commuting unit real pseudoscalar $I^2 = -1$. But then again it is not clear three generations are within reach. One should note that $Cl_{6,1}$ and Cl_7 are appealing because they provide a commuting pseudoscalar $I^2 = -1$ which is the volume element (from which cosmological constants are made as Lagrange multipliers).

A perhaps even more promising path to the Standard Model is with a doubling of the full 4D spacetime algebra (a 16-dimensional graded Clifford algebra). The conceptual idea is that up to similarity with Cl_8 the doubled STA has enough generators for a full three generations of chiral fermion Standard Model spinors. The only works we know supporting these claims are those of Gillard and Gresnigt [14] and Perelman [10], however the main concepts are not unrelated to all of the previously cited investigations. There is an intriguing potential link here, in that Lasenby [7] only obtains one generation, but doubles — via an ordered pair¹ — the $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ generators in doing so, and thus naively under-the-hood that construction might be related to the Cl_8 approaches of Perelman and Gillard & Gresnigt.

Perelman does not build a model in Cl_8 , but rather combines a Jordan algebra and a complexified Cl_4 . Without a real geometric meaning to the imaginary unit, we are free to do something else and use the pseudoscalar of $Cl_{6,1}$ to effectively double Cl_4 , and we can see the structure $Cl(4, \mathbb{C}) \equiv Cl_4$ as the STA with inclusion of a type of ‘Wick rotation’ (a duality transform in this case) doubled by the pseudoscalar of the $Cl_{6,1}$ or Cl_7 .

Yet another connecting linkage is the fact the spinors are usually taken to be in the even subalgebras, and so in Cl_8 will be within $Cl_8^+ \cong Cl_7$. It can be no algebraic coincidence that Cl_7 contains one generation of SM fermions [4] but lacks three. The room to triality permute the fermions occurs in Cl_8 because of non-physical pinor states in Cl_8 . (The pinors cannot be considered physical because they do not preserve probability current.)

Of all the research options available three or four stand out in terms of getting us three generations of fermions. This is important from our 4D spacetime view since three generations is predicted for the anomaly cancellations for supersymmetry in 4D spacetime [15]. These are,

1. Lisi’s biquaternions — though not written-up in pure Clifford algebra.
2. Furey’s $\mathbb{C}l_6$ (complexified Cl_6) — the challenge is to remove the uninterpreted complex numbers as well as undesirable linear dependencies.
3. Gillard and Gresnigt Cl_8 or Cl_8 — with the challenge of fitting into 4D spacetime algebra.

Lisi’s approach seems to offer the advantage that it reaches down to 4D spacetime, and this seems to be because Lisi is particularly interested in a so-called TOE (he desires to include the hypothetical graviton).

Furey’s approach seems like it could be made compatible with Gillard & Gresnigt, because in Clifford Algebra there is almost always a way to find a geometric meaning for \mathbb{C} numbers. The geometric ‘prejudice’ is that the \mathbb{C} numbers are hiding either bivector structure (rotation planes) or pseudoscalar structure (grade dualities). Even in electrical engineering, for example, with phases for representing microwave transmission and the like, there is a physical rotation taking place between components of the photon field, which has a spacetime pseudoscalar generator. The uninterpreted imaginary numbers should really only occur in pure mathematics, not in physics, according to this view.

Thus is also the case in orthodox quantum mechanics. The complex phase for the wavefunction is seen in the light of the STA Dirac theory as bivector or pseudoscalar geometry. This is now reconcilable with the probability amplitudes being square roots of classical probabilities, thanks in part to the work of Barandes [16]. Hestenes earlier provided the interpretation of the \mathbb{C} structure, which is precisely in the form of rotors (the even subalgebra elements of spacetime) which act on physical multivectors via sandwich products:

$$\text{Rotor} : R = e^{B/2}, \quad \text{Spinor} : \psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{\beta I} R.$$

here B is any bivector generator, so can combine space rotations and Lorentz boosts. The spinor acts on the algebra of observables (other multivectors) via,

$$M \rightarrow \psi M \tilde{\psi}$$

¹ Which appears not to be necessarily a \mathbb{C} structure.

where $\tilde{\psi}$ is Clifford reversion (reverses order of vectors in geometric products). From these products the statistical weight $\sqrt{\rho}$ becomes the probability. The factor $e^{\beta I}$ is a duality rotation mixing particle and antiparticle in the Dirac spinors. (The pseudoscalar $I = e_0 e_2 e_2 e_3$ induces grade dualities in the algebra.) The Born Rule for squaring the amplitudes to get the probability is then trivially explained. All the ‘mystery’ of quantum mechanics then shifts to entanglement and interference, which is not the subject of this paper (though see [16] for some insights).

Gillard & Gresnigt, like Furey, have no *physical* justifications for adding extra dimensions to the *algebraic* basis, but unlike Furey seem to avoid uninterpreted imaginaries. This could (and usually does) call into question whether 4D spacetime is the correct fundamental base marble of reality. However, too many other clues give physicists hints that we do live in a 4D spacetime. Thus, rather than interpret the extra algebraic dimensions as extra space dimensions as in some Kaluza–Klein theory, we are motivated to seek topological interpretations.

In the paper [14] Gillard & Gresnigt achieve a loose sort of unification of Stoica and Furey. Stoica and Furey both used the complexification $\mathcal{C}l_6$. It is not physically clear why Gillard & Gresnigt moving to the real algebra $\mathcal{C}l_8$ lifts the need for uninterpreted \mathbb{C} numbers, but one can perhaps think of it as acknowledging the full STA as being doubled. This was one of the significant motives for our present essay.

This ironically fits with the String Theory paradigm, because we would be saying the elementary particles are extended structures in 4D spacetime. Not modes of vibration of some abstract fields living upon spacetime. That field theoretic view is of course very popular, which is exactly why we do not wish to follow that route. Our aim is to look for a new approach. To be different for the sake of difference.

The question we will ask is what are we doing when adding algebraic basis vectors to the 4D STA of $\mathcal{C}l_{3,1}$? With our spacetime minimalism self-imposed constraint we can only imagine we are exploring spacetime topology, meaning homotopy, not holonomy.

We can continue, and we will for a paragraph or so, because it is important to acknowledge as many past efforts as possible, they are all good clues. One further convergence is that Ivan Todorov [6] has ‘gravitated’ towards $\mathcal{C}l_{10}$, which he finds ‘beautifully’ blends in the Standard Model. Gresnigt’s group have hinted their future efforts will look at $\mathcal{C}l_{10}$.

By this stage you would be forgiven for getting the feeling there is no one single choice of algebra for the standard Model. Many may suffice.

This is indeed what we have been drawn to thinking, but with some good reason. Which is that few of the other CA approaches begin with where entanglement and QM comes from. Normally some complexification is added as a last word, with some hand waving about raising and lowering operators, and that’s the end of their story. T4G theory flips this around.

We *begin* in T4G with spacetime and QM, and find the geometric algebra is merely a most suitable language for describing spacetime topology. Our difficulty is we do not know the spacetime topology of the elementary particles. Instead are merely axiomatically assuming the *internal space* Clifford frame basis is accounting for local 4D spacetime topology. Despite this flaw, it is a good research direction because there is no telling Nature what to do. The natural world does not *have* to use a Clifford algebra. But apparently perhaps *we do*, in our models.

Because GR is fully accounted for within $\mathcal{C}l_{3,1}$ and the Standard Model is fully accounted for in large enough CA’s (albeit with unwanted crud) a reasonable proposition is that spacetime really exists, and there is some topology that involves some physical symmetries, and you are not going to do any better than use a graded algebra for your description of such topology. You might use the full power of simplicial complexes and whatnot, but where are the physical symmetries there? Nowhere to be found, since you can have any old wild topology you like if you lack empirical data support.

T4G is further supported in choosing CA’s as a language tool because of our interpretation of *what spinors are*. To avoid redundancy we will discuss what spinors are in a dedicated §-II.C. Everyone knows *mathematically* what spinors are, but it is what they are doing in quantum theory that is the question.

* * *

For mathematicians, particularly topologists, reading this paper, we would ask you how you might incorporate Clifford algebra into the study of 4D geometric topology? The tools to hand in a Clifford algebra seem almost ready-made for topology, given we have graded elements. Bivectors are unit areas, trivectors unit 3-volumes, and the pseudoscalar a unit 4-volume, which should all be reminiscent of the usual ingredients in algebraic topology in the cell complex approach to homology.

Before moving to modelling choices, one other breadcrumb is worth drawing attention to is that the octonions \mathbb{O} , the maximal division algebra, exist inside the spacetime algebra $\mathcal{C}l_{3,1}$, specifically in the full even subalgebra. But with a catch. The octonion multiplication table (or Fano plane) cannot be made in $\mathcal{C}l_{3,1}$ with the geometric product. Instead a more complicated octonionic-STA multiplication is needed,

$$\psi \star \phi = \psi_+ \phi_+ + \psi_+ \phi_- + \psi_- \tilde{\phi}_+ + \tilde{\phi}_- \psi_-$$

for $\phi, \psi \in \mathbb{O}_{\text{STA}}$, with,

$$\psi_+ = \frac{1}{2}(\psi + \gamma_0 \psi \gamma_0), \quad \psi_- = \frac{1}{2}(\psi - \gamma_0 \psi \gamma_0).$$

There has been no topological interpretation for this result, and perhaps that is why Triality — which in most dimension=8 algebras is an automorphism — has not been yet found within the STA. Yet because the octonion algebra can be constructed in the STA, triality has to be there somewhere [2].

I.B. Model choices

There is no strong community consensus, even when we decide we are going to limit options by staying within the Clifford algebra sphere. Over time it looks like progress is being made and some paths seem to be converging.

Consider for example the prevalence of Cl_6 or the complexification denoted $\mathbb{C}l_6$.

What we would like to do is step back from the search through algebra structures, and limit further our options by imposing some physical presumptions. Research-wise this is formally no different to choosing particular algebras to explore, but in the sentient mind it can be quite a different mind-altering story.

Many authors drop down to matrix representations to use familiar tools. It is then not always clear whether the metric signature is playing an important role or not, for example in the appearance of $Cl_{6,1}$, $\mathbb{C}l_6$, and Cl_7 in the citations. But then the naïve question is why stop there? Why not Cl_{10} ? Why not Cl_{12} ? Because any ‘states’ (bivector generators let’s say) that have no physical correspondence can simply be discarded by imposing arbitrary superselection rules, or just plain old conservation of charge rules. These could in T4G context be thoroughly justified as topological censorship rules, or at least this is what we would seek. Our whole motto or paradigm is that *the algebra is a language, it is not the physics*.

What makes these explorations of potential SM algebras, or the underpinnings thereof, so disparate is that they are almost all abstract geometric algebra with no grounding in spacetime topology. The real geometry of Nature is only being guessed at, or worse, not even considered, swept under the rug, which invites us to pull back this rug and attempt to provide this and more physical picture.

It is then not a completely wild idea that a lot of dissimilarities could occur with, say, how the timelike basis vector is treated. We would like to point out that physically there is only one sensible way to double the STA to have two γ_0 basis vectors², which is that the particle topology is non-local in spacetime, hence if we apply a 4D spacetime manifold constraint this directly implies Planck scale wormhole topology. No one should be compelled to impose such a model constraint, it is just a model choice at this stage, but this is our particular preference.

Relations to the groups $\text{Spin}(8)$ and E_6 seem to be of interest for further “unifications.” Our present aims are *not* for further unifications, since in line with the Coleman–Mandula theorem, we are content in separating out the Lorentz transforms, or more in particular, 4D spacetime position and rotation gauging, as separate operations to the internal particle rotations. This is because

in T4G theory we do not need an elementary graviton. In addition, the LR-Symmetric Standard Model coupled with the CPT-Symmetric Big Bang [17, 18] provides us with an already supersymmetric Standard Model in 4D spacetime. The “cost” being only the introduction of a heavy RH neutrino and 36 dimension zero Bogoliubov scalars [19]. Of these, only ν_R (which is not presently directly observable) represents transforms for a propagating particle, so it is not a great cost.

All told the options for research are somewhat embarrassingly wide open, and the list of citations barely scratches the surface.

We *prefer* to use the Spacetime Algebra framework instead of “uninterpreted” quaternions and \mathbb{C} numbers. By contrast Lisi’s approach is also good to follow and contrast, since he uses the Lie algebra and Cartan subalgebras instead of more abstracted group theory which is implicit anyway. We can always probably abolish the quaternions and \mathbb{C} numbers in Lisi’s models by substituting them for bivectors and the complex structure of the pseudoscalar + scalar? However that may be, when physicists get into the groups, $\text{Spin}(8)$ and E_8 and all that, the level of abstraction often risks missing real geometry considerations. Whereas the Lie algebra is more local (by definition) and so easier to think about in terms of the bivectors of the frame bases in STA, and hence is our preferred level of analysis.

Our paper also has a different context to those others. We start from 4D spacetime only, and impose a theory constraint that we can have nothing else, it is self-imposed minimalism. With just this framework we can get a quantum theory by permitting ubiquitous wormhole-like topology. We say ‘wormhole-like’ because these are not classically traversable wormholes, they are Planck scale structure that permit nearly closed time-like curves, but nothing with more energy than a gravity wave or thereabouts can traverse these wormholes due to fairly well-understood topological censorship [20–22]. Meaning, if we cannot probe the wormhole topology, our probes at least have too much energy to traverse the ER-bridge without collapse, and including also the need for violation of energy conditions.

Obtaining a quantum theory is fairly weak, there are several frameworks which can be counted as ‘quantum mechanical’, and ever since sharp simpler axiomatizations [23, 24] were found the list of varieties of ‘QM’ has only grown³. Thus in modern context to be even slightly interesting a quantum mechanics model needs to reproduce the Standard Model of particle physics. We will be presumptuous and say this implies the left-right symmetric Standard Model with a \mathbb{Z}_2 symmetry, which has dark matter, ν_R , and a plausible small positive cosmological constant [15].

² Trayling & Baylis [4] have *time* as a scalar, making use of *paravectors*.

³ To what extent they are all physically isomorphic (meaning after nonphysical gauge and similar degrees of freedom are removed) is not our concern.

The Lie algebra for the left-right symmetric Standard Model is,

$$\mathfrak{su}(3)_C \oplus \mathfrak{su}(2)_L \oplus \mathfrak{su}(2)_R \oplus \mathfrak{u}(1)_{B-L}$$

An extra \mathbb{Z}_2 symmetry can be added as a discrete parity or charge conjugation symmetry that exchanges the $SU(2)_L$ and $SU(2)_R$ factors, enforcing left-right symmetry in the theory. The model is falsifiable in the near future, since there are bounds on the mass of the heaviest right-handed neutrino [15, 25].

We ask readers to stick to a 4D spacetime context for now, as a self-imposed constraint. Then what is at stake is whether we should regard our universe as: **(a)** like a billiard table with balls plonked onto it (fields ‘living on spacetime’); or **(b)** 4D spacetime fabric ‘all the way down’ albeit getting crumpled up and messy, though in an elegant symmetric way.

We do not reject gauge fibre models as unphysical *per se*. We just regard them as unnecessary. We take the somewhat extremist view (or minimalist to be more charitable) that any structure with gauge redundancy is abstraction, or accounting equipment, not physical ontology. Gauge fibre theory is tremendously useful in scattering theory and fundamental SM development, but no one is forced to take the gauge fields as actual physical stuff, the latter view is too strong an ontological commitment to be regarded as healthy metaphysics, in our opinion.

Can we also point out that strings and branes also “live” on spacetime, and are thus not the most parsimonious model for elementary particles one might imagine?

A more modest and minimalist research program might instead regard 4D spacetime topology as the only tools we have available. This is quite a sharp discipline, but it behoves the physics community to press this as far as can be compacted — or should we say expand it as far as can be reached! An historical lesson as precedent is *apropo*: The “perfect” candidate for dark matter considered in the 1970’s was abandoned merely because it was considered too difficult to propose how the right-handed neutrino could have been generated. This abandonment was a proverbial greatly exaggerated death [18].

In choosing an appropriate Clifford Algebra (CA) for our analysis some isomorphisms can be considered. Many authors use a complexified algebra, but we can immediately dismiss these noting,

$$\mathbb{C}l_{p,q} \cong Cl_{1,1} \otimes Cl_{p,q} \quad (1)$$

$$Cl_{p+1,q+1} \cong Cl_{p,q} \otimes Cl_{1,1} \quad (2)$$

The complexified Clifford Algebras (CCA) thus may always be reduced to real geometry with a bipartite (tensor) structure. That is good news on the face of it for T4G theory.

If we then try to “grow” to the maximal minimalist algebra, we would be tempted to consider the following⁴:

- (a) Double the STA — just to get transforms (and bilinear invariants) for each end of a wormhole separately. We can reach Cl_8 .
- (b) Incorporate cosmology considerations and asymptotics, so lift up to the conformal geometric algebra, then we have transforms for real dilations — the dilations from the statistical factor in ψ is not real geometry, it is statistical weight. We then can reach $Cl_{8+1,1} \cong Cl_{5,5}$ (the latter is a nice structure to work with).
- (c) For independent dilations on each wormhole end we could motivate lifting again to $Cl_{9+1,1+1} \cong Cl_{6,6}$.
- (d) Complexify any such choice of base CA, to explore the possibility of needing an extra “wormhole rotation” or “wormhole duality” transform — not knowing what this is in terms of spacetime topology, but allowing for the concept. We could perhaps reach Cl_{12} this way.

But these are just physical spacetime motivations. None of this so far is proper mathematical physics in the way, say, electromagnetism suggests $Cl_{3,1}$ is the correct language toolkit.

The thing is, we do not *know* the wormhole topology, so our research stance is that you should motivate any old Clifford Algebra you like with bipartite structure, and see if it works. It is a reverse engineering puzzle to figure out what the real spacetime topology might be.

For beginners, it is probably most instructive to begin exploring Cl_8 and $\mathbb{C}l_8$, the former because we manifestly get Triality, and the latter to explore structure of extra duality transforms and signature independence (in complexified CA’s the metric signature is irrelevant, $\mathbb{C}l_{p,q} \cong \mathbb{C}l_{p+q,0}$).

A motivation for this spacetime minimalism is discussed in §-I.C and in particular our outlook on what *quantum mechanics is really all about* is crucial in §-II.B for developing a realist pedagogical path for students to better understand our entire framework.

In this paper we work under the philosophical mindset of thinking of doubling or tripling the spacetime algebra (STA). Further motivation for this is discussed in §-II, then some results are reviewed in §-III.

I.C. Our Framework

Before discussing the algebraic results, it is important we feel to beg for sympathetic readers. We are working strictly within a chosen framework, a set of strong self-imposed constraints. Section II will do more to justify this framework, but without being aware of our framework up-front readers might get dissuaded from reading this paper and dismissing it due to some conflict with their favoured paradigm or framework.

This is a difficult hurdle for any new theory proposal. However, we’d like to point out some nice features of

⁴ For the isomorphisms we use see [26, chapter 16].

our framework without going into too much detail, and hopefully this will invite sympathetic readers, while not demanding anyone adhere to our view:

1. We are using Topological 4-Geon theory (T4G) — it is a gravitational explanation for quantum mechanics.[27]
2. T4GT [28, 29] had previously no explicit models for the elementary particles (or ‘fields’ if you prefer). The strictly 4D spacetime algebra (the Clifford algebra $Cl_{3,1}$ provides an excellent minimal language for T4G theorists, and this is what we employ. (It is not a bias for Clifford Algebra, you can repeat everything we do in matrix language.⁵)
3. We claim the Spacetime Algebra (STA) approach to the Standard Model is consistent with Turok & Boyle’s CPT-Symmetric cosmology and LR-symmetric Standard Model [17, 18], which means we inherit their solutions to from six to eight of the most outstanding particle physics problems: (1) resolution of the Big Bang singularity (it is a conformal CPT mirror boundary), (2) flatness, homogeneity and isotropy explained without an inflaton, (3) no primordial gravity waves, and a near gaussian CMBR spectrum with a small spectral tilt, (4) solution to the strong CP problem, and (5) exact Weyl, trace and vacuum anomaly cancellation at tree level that predicts exactly three generations of fermions.
4. In addition; (6) the natural dark matter candidate is the right-handed neutrino [18], (7) a small positive cosmological constant is most probable from full 4D spacetime entropy considerations, and lastly (8) the Higgs cannot be fundamental, and could be a composite of 36 dimension zero scalars (required for the aforementioned anomaly cancellations).
5. We have to extend $Cl_{3,1}$ to include non-trivial spacetime topology (4-geons).

If these are not motives enough for people to wish to study T4G theory then our cause is lost.

Granted these motivations, we are then faced with the question of which algebraic approach to use for modelling the wormhole topology in the context of a stochastic theory of measurements on spacetime boundaries (the latter being the quantum theory for the algebra, see our §-II and §-II.B).

Due to the near convergence of Furey, Stoica, Todorov, and Gillard & Gresnigt, we were motivated to consider

⁵ You think of a computer programming language analogy, you might think Matrix algebra for QM is like \mathbf{C} or C++ or even Assembly, while Clifford algebra is Python. We do not care for any such JargonFile ‘religiosity’ and we use Clifford Algebra because it is easiest for us. You may call it a crutch, and we say, “Yeah fine.”

the Cl_8 and Cl_{10} systems. These are however not all that dissimilar to: (i) Lasenby — who found he had to judiciously double the STA; and (ii) Trayling & Baylis — who use Cl_7 but have time as a scalar component (or replace vectors by paravectors) and perhaps as a consequence cannot find three generations of fermions; and (iii) although it seems harder to make contact with Lisi [8] (who uses biquaternions), the biquaternions are like a (complex) doubling of part of the even subalgebra of STA (the bivector part). One can get a complexification of the bivector subalgebra of the STA (closed under commutator product) by including the unit scalar and the pseudoscalar. So even Lisi’s approach starts to look poetically a lot like Gillard & Gresnigt. The link between them being Lasenby who attempts to align closely with Lisi, but in doing so needs a way of doubling the STA ($Cl_{3,1}$).

We should point out, the only reason we do not just borrow whole clothe from either Furey or Stoica, or the other complexified CA’s, is that we are seeking a geometrodynamics basis for fundamental physics, including the quantum mechanics, and so an uninterpreted complex unit imaginary is not acceptable (to us). Algebraically there is of course no problem in building the SM algebra using a complexification, but in our view that is formality devoid of real geometric insight.

The point being that if we have any uninterpreted algebraic primitives we imagine it would be very difficult to ‘reverse engineer’ the algebraic model to deduce the likely wormhole topology structure. There are some stringy-like models, such as Bilson-Thompson’s ribbon-graphs or ‘helons’ [30, 31], and so one would like to try to make connections with those ideas, because they are almost proverbial *quantum gravity*. Indeed there are hints it is possible to do so, see [13, 32] where Gresnigt maps braids to spinors from two complex Clifford algebras. Unfortunately these maps only carry one generation of fermions. These preon/helon ribbon models are nevertheless instructive and insightful for T4G, they provide two interesting intuitions:

1. twists along the ribbons of $\pm 2\pi$ seem to account for electrocolor symmetries,
2. the braid structure of the ribbons accounts for weak symmetry and chirality.

Many features of the topological side of this model are arbitrary, so cannot be taken seriously as physical reality. The mapping to the Clifford algebra — though still rather too formal looking — is a possible grounding in spacetime physics for such preon models [13].

We would also not say the preon model is “manifestly quantum gravity” because it has no account for entanglement and superposition. In the latest helon/preon effort [31] those researchers were putting in ‘quantum geometry’ by-hand (axiomatically). T4G does almost the re-

verse, we ‘emerge’⁶ quantum mechanics from the spacetime topolgy.

It is interesting to note that if we had no interest in 4D spacetime topology then we would be stopping with Gresnigt et al [12, 14] (or Furey or Stocia or Todorov), since they give us all the particle content we need, for T4G, since we are dropping the graviton from status of spacetime topology (the graviton is involved with spacetime holonomy). For their part, we believe Furey and Stocia are not resting on their models because they think they also need to find the graviton and the Higgs, whereas we do not. Hence from our point of view they have completed the job for us. However, the whole point of ‘doing T4G’ is that we *do care* about spacetime topology. Thus we do not want uninterpreted pure-and-only algebraic structure, nor seemingly arbitrary topological pictures.

In §II.C we will declare the topological 4-geon (T4G) view of the model theoretic status of the *elementary spinors*. This will help clarify our framework, and fit in the T4G physical approach to fundamental theory with the algebraic.

II. T4G DISCUSSION

Several authors before us have used Cl_6 or similar Clifford algebras within which they can find many aspects of the Standard Model. Perhaps without motivation? Or at least we found little geometric motivation with the significant exception of Anthony Lasenby [7]. In this paper so far we have had a distinct motivation in mind: we double — or triple, in the light of the helon ribbon model — the 3-space sector of our Lie algebra (and Clifford algebra) precisely because we desire to account for Planck scale wormhole topology.

What this “accounting” is exactly is not in our present purview, we are not expert algebraic topologists. So here the deeper mathematical aspects of our work are only meant to be suggestive, or suggested. What we can offer is some distinctly *physical motivations*.

We now outline briefly aspects of T4G that are needed as motivations for the T4G version of the Standard Model. This will not be a seminal review, just a quick glance. We refer readers to [27] for a few more specifics.

II.A. Cobordism boundaries define measurements

In T4G theory all we have available is 4D spacetime. Wormhole topology structure yields quantum mechanics [27, 33]. The basic quantum mechanical structure in T4G is a partial spacetime cobordism. This is a spacetime region between two spacelike hypersurfaces ∂M_1

and ∂M_2 . This restricted notion of cobordism is called a T4G-cobordism.

Taking a Minkowski frame (or *lens* really) — hence ignoring Planck scale non-trivial topology — we would normally want to include all spacetime events accessible via light-cones from ∂M_1 as being what define ∂M_2 .

The measurement problem of QM is resolved within this framework (only if this framework is correct to some extent⁷). We define a measurement to be the preparation of the particle configuration space on ∂M_1 and the detection measurements on the boundary ∂M_2 . What happens in the interior of the T4G-cobordism is completely inaccessible. If a probe was made of the cobordism interior t , for $t_1 < t < t_2$, then that just redefines ∂M_2 to be ∂M_t .

It is more correct to say this T4G-cobordism region defines ‘an experiment’, since the measurements occur only on the boundaries.

There is no collapse of a wave function because there is no wave function. As Barandes [16] has pointed out, when the dynamics are non-Markov and indivisible, they automatically imply entanglement structure in the interior, as well as superposition. However, it is important to note that this is only a statistical account for entanglement, the non-Markov dynamics cannot possibly account for spacetime topological aspects of entanglement, which is why we need T4G theory, namely in order to provide an explanation for the quantum–stochastic correspondence[35].

Superposition is *almost*⁸ nothing but a statistical phenomenon (so not a real phenomenon *per se*). Interference — for single particles — is defined precisely as the failure of the stochastic transition from ∂M_1 to ∂M_2 to be divisible (implying failure to be Markov⁹).

In the T4G view the indivisible stochastic dynamics is not generating entanglement, the causality is the other way around; it is because of entanglement that the generic spacetime cobordism is described by indivisible stochastic dynamics. T4G goes even further and suggests entanglement is not mere spooky correlation (as in orthodox QM) but is rather a real consequence of 4D wormhole topology. There is some justification for this, see the preprint [27].

The logic of measurement propositions on the T4G cobordism boundaries is precisely Quantum Logic [36]. The proof involves acknowledging simply that at the Planck scale information can traverse nearly closed time-like curves, which exist due to topological 4-geon structure which T4G presumes exist (axiomatically). The distant past and distant future of a boundary ∂M_2 thus provide non-redundant data. (Because wormhole topology

⁶ ‘Emergence’ is the wrong idea, and is devoid of mathematical content. We would prefer to simply say that QM can be derived from T4G theory.

⁷ Similarities with the operator algebra of a ‘smeared’ worldline can be inferred [34].

⁸ We explain why superposition is not *entirely* statistical in [27].

⁹ Strictly speaking, indivisible stochastic dynamics are a subset of all non-Markov dynamical processes — but a special subset, namely the quantum mechanical subset.

is at the Planck scale, but two ends of a wormhole can get arbitrarily far apart in space or time, up to Tsirelson bounds.) In this case a strict Hamiltonian time-evolution account cannot determine the configuration of particles on the boundary. The ‘experiment’ must thus presume only at best an entire equivalence class of 3-manifolds for ∂M_2 . (By the same token also for ∂M_1 .)

The equivalence class of submanifolds $[\partial M_2]$ is defined by the measurement set-up, since this is what determines (semi-classically) the possible observables that are going to be recorded. If the laboratory at $t = t_1$ changes the set-up with some $\Delta t = \delta$ messing about, that just redefines $t_1 \rightarrow t_1 + \delta$ to the later time after the new set-up is completed.

Note that T4G is thus unabashedly classical & quantum — at the same time. The classical world surely ‘exists’ and yet involves quantum mechanics ubiquitously. Classicality is not a separate physics in T4G, it ‘exists’ alongside QM, and is nothing but what we get whenever we can ignore entanglement structure. For two systems A and B separated by enough space or time then they will be relatively classical, since there is no *discernable* entanglement between them, while internally they will evolve quantum mechanically as described by the indivisible stochastic dynamics from their respective $\partial M_{1,i}$ to $\partial M_{2,i}$ boundaries, $i \in \{A, B\}$.

The subtlety is that there really is no clear boundary between any two systems, there is only a division in an operational sense: namely whenever you do not care about any entanglement between your defined systems. This is not a subjectivist theory. ‘You’ here means you as a laboratory. Anything could be considered a laboratory if it leaves behind recordings some ‘mind’ (i.e., a scientist doing their science, or just doing their grocery shopping) can later inspect. We are all scientists. Some just nerdier and more precise than others.

Even classically, the equivalence class $[\partial M_2(\hat{x}_A)]$ corresponding to position measurements of a ‘particle’ represented by, say, a spinor ψ_A , is *incompatible with the equivalence class for measurements of momentum* for the same particle $[\partial M_2(\hat{p}_A)]$. This just means these two equivalence classes form disjoint sets.

The proof of disjointness could use some work, it is mostly axiomatic for now (see [33]) but we believe it could be structured with more primitive axioms, we would only need a reason why non-trivial spacetime topology implies measurements of incompatible observables cannot be made on the same equivalence classes $[\partial M_2]$. The point being not to assume the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle, we would instead be laying a topological foundation for the HUP. (T4GT cannot assume QM axioms, but must derive them, otherwise we have a circular theory, which we feel is not a good variety of bootstrapping.)

In our view this makes the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle not truly fundamentally quantum, it is classical as well, but with no Planck constant of relevance in the usual frameworks for CM the HUP just does not get accounted for, even though it really is implicit. What

instead distinguishes classicality from quantum mechanics is entanglement structure, or equivalently in the GPT framework [37] the fact the state transitions in QM are reversible *and continuous* — in classical mechanics state transitions are only reversible.

The result of this T4G boundary classification is a non-distributive orthomodular lattice of measurement propositions. A quantum logic in other words.

This is only one way of deriving QM from extension of GR to non-trivial topologies. Another is to use the idea of quantum channels and Choi states to show the stochastic theory of spacetime cobordisms for GR with CTCs yields indivisible stochastic transition probabilities. This also implies quantum mechanics via Barandes’ results [16, 27].

In summary, T4G implies the quantum mechanical aspects in GR are due to non-trivial spacetime topology, and quantum mechanics proper is defined on the T4G-cobordism boundaries. (So orthodox QM is a variety of Holographic Theory already, in plain FRWL spacetimes).

There is no problem with having a partial holographic theory for QM like this, because we do at the end of the day want classical physics to be not merely some abstract limit, but a real limit of the stochastic dynamics in the context when entanglement structure is of little to no physical relevance for measurement outcomes (by either coarse graining or explicit breaking of entanglement structure). This would be the T4G resolution of Frauchiger–Renner generalized Wigner Friends paradoxes [38]. To wit: measurements do break (and reform elsewhere) entanglement structure, yielding *real* classical appearances, not merely Relative States [39].

Elsewhere we have a preprint [40] showing how T4G theory resolves the EPR Paradox — better said to be a tension between locality, causality, statistical independence, and determinism (or Reichenbach Common Cause). All those cherished principles that are a bedrock of science can be retained while still getting the required violation of Bell’s inequalities when entanglement is identified as causal ER-bridge structure.

It is well-understood that the EPRB experiments violate the measurement logic of classical mechanics, hence there is still something that T4G must abandon. In unorthodox fashion T4G theory claims that quantum mechanics is incomplete. Others propose the same conclusion but from very different arguments [41].

II.B. Quantum theory of elementary particles

We assume familiarity with the QFT paradigm. T4GT can accommodate QFT by lifting the non-Markov particle stochastic theory to a stochastic dynamics model with topology change. Non-relativistic QM is already the stochastic theory, but does not incorporate topology change (does not have Fock space raising and lowering operators).

One gives up on knowledge of particle worldlines, for good reason in T4GT — because they are influenced by

data on the future boundaries of any given spacetime cobordism region. All aspects of QM otherwise come from entanglement structure, which has only one possible explanation under the constraint of 4D spacetime, namely wormhole topology. One can say with the empirical success of QM then imposing an additional assumption that all we have is a 4D spacetime is effectively a proof that wormholes are implied by the theory.

An alternative view of physical reality is to consider the elementary particles as fundamental, and spacetime as an illusion. For example Finster thinks all is made from “causal fermions” [42]. Or, closer to T4G/STA views, Furey [43] speculates ‘causality’ is nothing but an algebra acting upon itself. Spacetime can then be ‘built’ by combining a subset of the algebra’s basis vectors. But what are these basis vector primitives? In Furey’s vision they are nothing but constructs needed to generate the particle states. We do not subscribe to this view because we have an almost inverse view of what the ‘states’ are in a given quantum theory.

Just looking at an algebra for the particles is an incomplete picture of quantum physics, because it leaves aside the measurement process. The measurement process is fundamental to quantum theory though! It cannot be ignored, and is really at the heart of many of the perplexing aspects of quantum physics. Even to the point where some schools of thought give up on emergence of classical reality and argue there are no measurements other than what a subsystem subjectively ‘perceives’ (whatever that may mean for a non-sentient subsystem¹⁰).

We stipulate — as one of our model axioms, or really an interpretation of some mathematics — that the spinors are transformation instructions which act on the algebra of spacetime observables. Thus in expressions like,

$$M \rightarrow \langle \psi M \tilde{\psi} \rangle_S$$

the observable represented mathematically in the model by some multivector M , is what we associate with a physical experiment, and as in orthodox QM the eigenvalues will be the real valued outcomes we read off from instruments of various sorts, which in the above expression is indicated by the bra-ket which in the Clifford algebra formulation of QM is the grade projection operator, and the subscript S says we are projecting onto the scalar part.

More precisely, “an experiment” is more accurately represented by the ‘arrow’ in the above expression. It

is like a functor from the space of abstract observables to real numbers.

Although it is hard to find any theoretician who reduces *real* experiments to such fine grain primitives, few physicists would doubt that this is a valid interpretation of the measurement processes *as modelled by a quantum mechanics* theory.

What the orthodox view says is that the ψ are the physical elements, and the M are the “instruments” (primitive ways to model the experimental apparatus). QFT then lifts the ψ up to more abstract fields in order to accommodate pair production and annihilation.

That’s the orthodox view.

In T4G theory we do *not* regard the ψ as the elements of physical reality. Instead the spinors are transformation instructions, acting as in the above expression $\psi M \tilde{\psi}$. It is more realistic to say that the multivector M is closer to an element of physical reality. But really it is neither. As just explained, the arrow in that expression is a process, a highly idealized measurement process.

Note that in the generally accepted rigorous development of QFT (see [44, Sec. 8.2]), using the Wightman scheme, the *quantum fields*, ϕ , are regarded as operator-valued generalized functions on Minkowski spacetime \mathcal{M} , not as ‘fields defined at each point of spacetime’. In such schemes it is thus clear that the elementary particles we observe in Nature are *not* quantum fields. The quantum fields are descriptions of functions that we employ in order to describe results of our measurements on the particles. This at least to our minds is the clearest conception of QFT. It is consistent with the T4G prescription we have given in the NRQM case where the spinors are transformation instructions, so also Clifford-valued functions on the spacetime manifold.

To obtain a QFT from T4G+STA we can just re-employ a scheme like Wightman’s and promote the spinors to raising and lowering operators using the usual Fourier mode expansion for the generalized functions on the spacetime. All this does is lift the indivisible stochastic dynamics from single particle wavefunctions to Fourier or raising and lowering coefficients in the multi-particle Fock space of a QFT.

What then are the ‘elements of reality’ in T4G theory?

The answer we hold is that at a basic level where things like souls and minds are not even part of the discussion, the raw physics is just 4D spacetime topology, and nothing more. Thus to conduct quantum physics with the raw elements of reality would mean dropping down a level to *spacetime geometrodynamics*. This is generally today considered far too impractical. Indeed, we would have no idea how to even begin, except with numerical simulations of a spacetime manifold and using concepts familiar from GR, but now with non-trivial topology altering geodesics in addition to curvature. This could rightly be regarded as beautiful madness. The concept is clear and simple, the implementation of calculations extraordinarily hard.

For mere mortals, the only alternative appears to be

¹⁰ One *could* mean by this that the subsystem (which could be a few elementary particles) merely has a record or ‘memory’ of events that can be regarded as ‘measurement history’. But in the Relative State Interpretations of QM the history is not objective nor universal, it is a history for in principle *only* that subsystem. Which implicates issues of what we physicists even mean when we talk about objective physics and objective reality. This sort of philosophy borders upon madness, so is not our view, especially because we have a better alternative explanation (not a mere interpretation) of quantum mechanics.

lifting back up to a stochastic dynamics description. This explains why our development of T4G theory is at the same level as quantum mechanics. We dare not go deeper. Hopefully some day others can.

II.C. What are spinors?

We have already implicitly answered this question. In the Clifford algebra context spinors are almost nothing but the even subalgebra for our algebraic theory. Every spinor has a generic form:

$$\psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{\beta I} R$$

although in the full Standard Model the rotors, R , are not only the Dirac–Pauli spacetime bivectors, but will include more general “topological” generators. Every spinors also has a statistical factor, ρ , but this is for classical probability densities. This is so far only semi-physical.

What we want to elaborate upon now is how these algebraic structures fit in with orthodox QM.

The full physical meaning of the spinors is that they are transformation instructions. They *act on* the multivector algebra of observables, as we pointed out earlier: $M \rightarrow \psi M \psi$, in Clifford algebra these adjoint actions are the basic linear transformations. This inverts the orthodox point of view which tends to see the observables as acting upon the spinors. We think the switch in point-of-view is important, at least for mental clarity.

The reason why the orthodox psychology was/is “the observables act on the wavefunction” is in our opinion due to bad algebraic design, namely the use of the matrix algebra, rather than the more natural Clifford algebra. The motto is that the matrix obscures the real geometry. (Uninterpreted imaginaries, conflation of geometric graded elements with “complex amplitudes,” hence confounding the statistical content of spinors with the geometric content and so forth).

For the same reason, we prefer to keep clear of the octonion and sedenion approaches to triality, because, although to a lesser extent than the matrix algebra, these algebras obscure the real geometry.

Mathematically a **spinor space** is defined as a *minimal left (or right) Ideal of a Clifford algebra*. This is not much good for a physicist unless it can be connected to real spacetime structure. The decomposition of a spinor into statistical and rotor parts is our preferred “more physical” definition, which implies for theoretical development and application to quantum theory we need to make a connection between; (i) this view of ‘physical spinors’ as transformation instructions acting on the multivector observables, and (ii) the minimal left ideals of the Clifford algebra. The first step towards this is recognition that the *physical spinor* is not an element of physical reality, it is a transformation instruction, which acts within a mathematical model on the mathematical model’s representations of elements of reality (observables).

To say more about how we conceive of the multivectors as ‘elements of reality’ would take us into more philosophical depth than we care or need, so we will leave that interpretation issue to others. Suffice it to say, whenever we detect an elementary particle, it is always in one location in spacetime, up to experimental precision. The experimentalists arbitrary laboratory frame has to be oriented to align with the elementary particle’s in order to extract any (truncated) real number result for science communication. But all multivectors in the Clifford algebra are constructed from the basic operations of the algebra (geometric products) on the basis vectors. So the action of the spinor on the basis vectors is all we need for definable observables.

For pedantry, to put this in more pedantic pedagogical terms, when say a particle’s velocity is measured the experimentalist records two positions (\vec{x}_1, t_1) and (\vec{x}_2, t_2) , and can compute some 3 numbers and call them \vec{v} . Suppose that obtained $\vec{x}_1 = (1, 2, 0)$, $\vec{x}_2 = (3, 5, 4)$. But the physical particle current was always $\psi \gamma_0 \psi$, regardless of the experimentalists numbers \vec{v} . To say something with physical meaning the experimentalist must consult a theorist (let’s imagine!) and figure out what her rather arbitrary numbers mean, given they might have set up totally different ‘ruler’ orientations for measuring their \vec{x}_1 and \vec{x}_2 — say recording $\vec{x}_1 = (0, 5, 10.89)$, $\vec{x}_2 = (-2.02, 4, 6)$ — and only then can the experimentalist say what the ‘state’ ψ must have been on their measurement boundary. They can for example say, $v^2 = 29$ for that ψ . But in T4G theory, they are not saying “ ψ has the property $v^2 = 29$,” they are saying the action of ψ on γ_0 projected onto γ_0 , then squared, was equal to 29 (in their STA-QM model).

The particle’s physical status is all in the particle frame’s γ_0 , and the experimentalists ψ is something concocted by the experimentalist, and has *mathematical* ‘properties’ (only in their model) deduced after the fact. The ψ has no physical properties, it is a piece of a model, which could now be used to predict something about the subsequent motion of the particle.

To put this bluntly, the basis vectors once projected onto the intrinsic frame of an elementary particle are the fundamental observables.

To be more blunt:

1. the Clifford basis is a frame field (abstract, non-physical);
2. the spinors (or their actions) are transformations from laboratory to elementary particle.
3. The observables are (typically scalar) parts (grade projections) of those transformations.

There is only one slight abuse of terminology here, which is that we have used ‘multivector observables’ to mean not the multivectors themselves (which are abstract) but the truncated real numbers resulting from the grade projections 3.

What are spinors then?

We first need to choose a model for the quantum theory. We have chosen a spacetime with non-trivial topology. For observables we choose the multivectors of the Clifford algebra generated by frame vectors (technically the frame basis vectors of the cotangent space of the spacetime manifold).

In the simplest framework, the ‘elements of reality’ in such a quantum theory model are the multivectors of the Clifford algebra.

The take-away:

Spinors are transformation instructions.

This means the *whole thing* $\psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{\beta I} R$, all of it. The statistical factor is a simple x dependent dilation transform instruction, but preserves probability — the other factors have the unitary property $R\tilde{R} = 1$.

One last thing about spinors: if we desire or need to use more exotic transformations in some theory, like conformal transformations, then the construct of ψ will have additional conformal transformation factors other than the boosts and rotations from R .

II.D. Why Clifford Algebra ‘just works’

It is clear why Clifford Algebra $Cl_{3,1}$ ‘just works’ for General Relativity. Spacetime curvature is adequately accounted for with either set of tools from the toolbox containing, (i) tensor calculus, (ii) diff-forms, (iii) grade algebras over \mathbb{R} . Clifford algebra is in the toolset (iii). Either of these three tool boxes will suffice.

It might be less clear why CA ‘just works’ for the Standard Model. After all, if you accepted the orthodox views of either String Theory or QFT, then there is no reason at all why your favoured Lagrangian would be physically indistinguishable from a Lagrangian written in terms of the symmetry-respecting dimensionally correct scalar projections from a Clifford algebra.

But if you think that way you might have been taking Lagrangian spacetime QFT too much for granted. One thing everyone knows is that there are many choices for terms in Lagrangians that reproduce the same physics. It is one of the annoying splinters in the mind about Lagrangian or path integral formulations of QM and QFT. What ‘stuff’ chucked into your Lagrangian is real, and what is of the nature of fictional Fadeev–Popov ghost and so forth? This might be something most QFT practitioners just get trained to not care about — the “shut up and calculate” subculture.

T4G theory has, we think, a much more healthy attitude. This is the concept that with a Lagrangian we are in effect counting spacetime entropy — literally *counting*. The QFT counting is very different to classical statistical mechanics entropy calculation due to the not only non-equilibrium dynamics in a QFT, but the topology

change as well, which is highly non-classical. This subject however, deserves an entire separate treatise, and for our present purposes it should suffice to give just a hint of why the Clifford Algebras ‘just work’ which does not get into the deeper aspects of what whole 4D spacetime entropy computation involves.

What I have chosen, for illustration, is due to the Clifford Algebra design in the Marcel Reisz & David Hestenes schools, which is the simplest to read. This is the design employed above, and throughout this paper. The geometric product of two grade=1 vectors is,

$$ab = a \cdot b + a \wedge b$$

which has the obvious symmetric and anti-symmetric parts. The first term is the inner product, the second the outer product. With outer products of orthonormal basis vectors (the $\{e_i, i \in 1 \dots D\}$) there is an obvious induced Clifford algebra on any vector space.

Space rotations and Lorentz boosts are generated by unit bivectors, like $e_{12} = e_1 \wedge e_2$, or $e_{30} = e_3 e_0$ where e_0 is the pure timelike vector in any given $Cl_{D-1,1}$ basis. The rotation (or boost) transform for any pure blade multivector is,

$$A \rightarrow RA\tilde{R}, \quad R = e^{B/2}$$

for some bivector B . We say “double sided transform,” or *sandwich product*. It is a distinct symbolic design advantage over matrix algebra. Restricting to 4D spacetime now, the rotors R are elements in the even subalgebra $Cl_{3,1}^+$. The transform of another rotor, say ψ , under a space rotation or boost can be easily seen from how an arbitrary vector transforms under the composite,

$$\begin{aligned} a &\mapsto R(\psi a \tilde{\psi})\tilde{R} \\ &= (R\psi)a(R\tilde{\psi}) \end{aligned}$$

and hence a rotor (or spinor) like ψ itself transforms as $\psi \mapsto R\psi$. Same for Lorentz transformations.

The terminology is that the spacetime transformations *act from the left*.

It is merely by design of the algebra!

To see this, towards a contradiction, suppose we attempt to let a gauge transform act on the left, i.e.,

$$\psi(x) \mapsto R(x)\psi(x)$$

What could go wrong? There are three problems, (1) the Dirac equation transformation fails, (2) the observable currents become inconsistent, (3) gauge fields cannot be consistently coupled on the left. We will only pursue (2). Take a physical observable like the Dirac current:

$$J = \psi \gamma_\mu \tilde{\psi}$$

Under $\psi \rightarrow R\psi$, we have,

$$J \mapsto R\psi \gamma_\mu \tilde{\psi} \tilde{R} = RJ\tilde{R}$$

That is: the internal phase rotation $R = e^{\alpha(x)I}$ now rotates spacetime vectors like J , which it should not do. It should only be rotating the spinor frame vectors γ_μ .

But for EM since I commutes with all spacetime vectors (because it's a pseudoscalar), so this doesn't *appear* to cause problems at first glance for EM. However, the real problem shows up when you go to nonabelian gauge group. For instance, SU(2) or SU(3) transformations do not commute with spacetime vectors or bivectors.

Thus, if gauge rotors act on the left, they interfere with the Lorentz structure of observables like $\psi\gamma_\mu\psi$, leading to incorrect transformations of currents and coupling terms. We conclude that left-acting gauge rotors contaminate the spacetime frame structure.

Given this design, the internal topological rotations for the elementary particles of the Standard Model must then *act on the right*. For if not we would obtain an inconsistency. (Physical inconsistency that is, the algebra design would otherwise not be applicable to physics.)

Note that if you regard ψ as a *physical object* you get nonsense, since in CA all physical objects rotate the same, no matter their grade, so you would rotate a physical ψ by $\psi \mapsto R\psi\bar{R}$. You would obviously lose the role of ψ as the original rotor. In other words, *rotors* and thus also spinors *are not physical objects!* Which is consistent with our T4G view of quantum mechanics from §II.C.

This T4G framework is probably compatible with fibre bundle techniques, but T4G is manifestly real spacetime geometry, whereas fibre bundles are, we feel, abstractions used merely for convenience. In the T4G framework Isotopic or 'internal' does not mean fibre bundles, it means there is fine scale topological structure.

II.E. Some terminology

The language we use has undeniable psychological impact, which can bias investigation, for good or for bad. Here we would like to proffer a few of our own biases, for the good.

We use the term **symmetry transforms** as a catch-all for both the bosons and fermions. This is not quite accurate, so hides a bias. Recall the spinors (fermions) are transformation instructions *acting on the algebra of observables*. So they are not *the* symmetry transformations *per se*. It would be better to think of the representations for the bosons as the symmetry transforms, but technically we want 'symmetry transform' to refer to the elements in the algebra as they act upon each other.

It is only because in the Clifford algebra that the category of physical observables is also valued in the same algebra that we can sometimes find it convenient to drop the distinctions between symmetry transformations and the spinors. However, when we use the language 'symmetry transforms' we hope the context is clear, and that there is an implied functorial mapping, not an identity relation. One category is the pure algebra, and the other is physical spacetime topology. The algebra is intended

to capture the relations between topologies in spacetime.

To be clear: the spinors have two roles. They act on the pure algebra, and as such are symmetry transformations. But for the Standard *Model* we are providing a physical layer, an interpretative layer, and then the spinors are not just about symmetry in the algebra, but rather elements in the algebra are singled out as corresponding to instructions for transformations on the algebra objects which represent physical observables, which is a category theoretic relation.

Presuming the algebra we judiciously choose captures all the physically relevant transformations is what justifies our loose uncategorical language when referring to the spinors as 'symmetry transformations'.

The whole problem with the Clifford Algebra Standard Model models is in trying to find a judicious choice of algebra.

It is important to highlight these language abuses or shortcuts, in this case in particular because there is a double layer of potential mental bias or confusion. A mathematician might never do this, but we are trying to also make our work readable, and so are prepared to suffer this trade-off between precision and readability. The two are not always in conflict, as greater precision can aid the reader, but nevertheless, we hope we strike a decent balance. As Clifford Algebra becomes more familiar to mainstream physicists it might later become possible to write more mathematically precisely.

II.F. Other 'Beyond the Standard Model' considerations

There is a useful approach to Clifford Algebra BSM (beyond the Standard Model) in a preprint by Wei Lu [45]. Lu discusses naturalness problems, the mass hierarchy puzzle and the Higgs. The Higgs is composite in Lu's model, which is an emerging trend or theme in a lot of unorthodox approaches to BSM. It is almost becoming mainstream [15, 19, 46].

Focusing on Lu's approach, we get some non-standard ideas even for Clifford algebraicists. One for example is Lu's insistence the Dirac γ_0 should or could be thought of as a trivector,

$$\gamma_0 = \Gamma_1\Gamma_2\Gamma_3$$

with the Γ_i being 'internal structure'. This somewhat makes a mockery of the Hestenes-Dirac spinor theory, but formally would be compatible if one were to just be analysing monogenic function theory. It remains to be seen if there is any real meaning in Lu's framework, but it is at least something to bear in mind. Our take would be that with a duality transform we can restore 'democracy' [47, 48] which enables one to view the correspondence as a duality mapping (anti-involution in 4D) $\gamma_0 \mapsto \Gamma_0 = I\gamma_0$, with $I = \gamma_0\gamma_1\gamma_2\gamma_3$ the spacetime algebra pseudoscalar (the unit 4-volume element).

However, we cannot then interpret these as spacetime frame vectors, because Lu also needs an independent set $\{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ for the original Dirac algebra $\{\gamma_\mu\}$. Hence Lu uses a Cl_6 basis,

$$\{\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, \Gamma_3, \gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3\}$$

which others would write as $\{e_i, f_i\}, i \in 1, 2, 3$.

What Lu is really doing is using Cl_8 (add γ_0 and Γ_0), but collapsing the two time coordinates to one, throwing away Γ_0 , which is of course reasonable in a point-particle context, where the local Lorentz frame can only have one timelike basis vector.

What we want to bear in mind is the wider concept of Clifford Algebra flexibility. Because CA is just a language, we are always free to impose alternative interpretations. The only horror story of theoretical physics is if we find a suitable algebra for the SM or BSM and then find that it has multiple realizations. But this is a distinctly “let’s cross that bridge when we get to it” story.

Another of Lu’s view points is worth a few more paragraphs.

II.G. Consideration of \mathbb{C} numbers

Wei Lu [45] points out the \mathbb{C} structures in the classical side of BSM physics is all in *real* Clifford Algebra, but then Lu insists the *quantum field theory* cannot dispense with uninterpreted \mathbb{C} numbers. We have been unable to pin-point why Lu thinks this way, but there is a T4G way to understand this point of view.

In T4G theory the fields are all fictional accounting tools, employed to account for indivisible stochastic dynamics. The evaluation via Feynman diagrams of the path integrals in QFT are thus free to use any old tricks needed to return sensible computational results.

So like a Wick rotation can be used to evaluate real integrals over \mathbb{R}^n , there need be no qualms about utilizing \mathbb{C} numbers in order to evaluate loop diagrams.

From our perspective we should not need uninterpreted \mathbb{C} numbers in the quantum theory, since it is still a real spacetime theory. Thus the evaluation of the path integrals for loop diagrams using \mathbb{C} numbers is not an indication that quantum mechanics is mysteriously non-classical because it requires \mathbb{C} numbers. For, (a) QFT does not *require* \mathbb{C} numbers, (b) non-classicality is always about entanglement structure, not pure algebra, and (c) if \mathbb{C} analysis is convenient for evaluating the consequences of non-Markov stochastic dynamics and topology change in the time evolution, then we may presume that is all the \mathbb{C} numbers are doing — conveniently aiding calculations.

But the real issue is that \mathbb{C} numbers can be useful all throughout various branches of analysis. But in quantum theory we have a marvellously complicated topic to deal with, and with several areas where analysis is applied, and two in particular being the spinors and the terms in the SM Lagrangian (the kinetic/dynamics side), and the other being in the non-Markov stochastic dynamics (the

probability side). When we use *only* the \mathbb{C} numbers we risk conflation, and failures of distinguishing the different meanings of the unit imaginaries. This is more than a significant reason to avoid the \mathbb{C} numbers in the SM Lie and Clifford algebra.

There is one clear justification for introducing a unit imaginary in T4G theory, which is as a phase for worm-hole oscillations. This is practically necessary, required one might say, in order to account for EPR correlations (since T4G does not employ abstract or statistical concepts as uninterpreted structure, such as entanglement added metaphysically by brute correlation. However, it is still somewhat unclear to us how this plays with the real Clifford Algebras, and one might be advised to complexify their Clifford algebra with care, which is to say, with a clear purpose — not just in order to “extract the Standard Model” (algebraic fundamentalism).

That said, there should be pure real geometric ways to introduce the ER=EPR wormhole geometrodynamics, and we would think of using a unit imaginary phase as more an ersatz, than a complete picture. For example, a dynamical wormhole collapse is hardly going to be truly modelled by a complex phase. The \mathbb{C} numbers we would say are acting in the probability framework, not in the spacetime geometrodynamics *per se*.

II.H. Other topological considerations

In this section we briefly gather a few speculative ideas to further motivate our later explorations.

The ‘Steuckelberg trick’¹¹ is a well known use of Feynman diagrams (Stueckelberg diagrams really) to explain pair production and annihilation as an inherently non-classical effect of turning a particle around in time to account for the antiparticle.

In a 4D spacetime view, there is no such things as moving around in time, there are only worldlines or world tubes. But in any case, the pair production and annihilation processes involve spacetime topology change, no matter how you slice things, even if your spacetime is emergent from something more primitive.

Related to the Steuckelberg trick are raising and lowering operators, which are what the pure field theory uses to account for particle creation or annihilation.

In the Clifford algebra approach an even algebra $Cl_{n,n}$ always has a Witt basis decomposition. The Witt basis vectors are null vectors, and as such are rather familiar to quantum field theorists, they arise even for graduate students in the theory of the quantum harmonic oscillator, the most well-used toy model of all.

In elementary particle physics we do not have particles in potential wells to deal with, since that’s a whole higher

¹¹ As distinct from the ‘Stueckelberg action’ which is about scalar quantities inserted into Lagrangians to generate mass without introducing gauge anomalies.

level sort of model. This begs the question, what are the raising and lowering operators doing appearing in the basic Clifford Algebras? — from a physicists point of view of course.

From a physicists point of view the mathematical structures could always just be coincidental.

However there is a motive for using the Witt basis as raising and lowering operators for the symmetry transformations in the Standard Model the Clifford algebra is as a language describing. Namely we have topology change whenever particles are created or destroyed. In relativistic QM we certainly do have particle creation and annihilation, so the symmetries associated with such topological transformations would be nice to have in one's algebra.

One might say it is a lucky coincidence of course¹² but then we do not believe in luck. Those algebras without raising and lowering operators presumably could not well-describe the quantum mechanics of our universe.

We believe that ladder operators are not found in all Clifford algebras, at least not in the Fock space sense in the form of the canonical commutation relations for raising and lowering operators. However, a complexified Cl_{2n} always has a Witt basis, since it has no specific signature. One might now speak of a coincidence if an even Cl turned out to yield the full Standard Model, but again we would hesitate, since although manifolds with local tangent spaces and a metric Clifford algebras are universal, for modelling T4G theory we would be inclined to choose an even algebra, just because we want to model the ER-bridge structure in some fashion — an inherently bipartite structure.

Moreover, there could be a deep connection between bipartite spacetime structure and particle creation & annihilation, though to date we are not aware of a strong formalized link, only our present speculations.

* * *

This brings to an end discussion of our main philosophical motivations. We now turn to developing these ideas.

III. BIPARTITE ALGEBRA MODELS

For our purposes a bipartite or split algebra has ‘democratic’ basis vectors, for example $\{\vec{e}_i\}$ and $\{\vec{f}_i\}$, $i \in 1, 2, 3$, and the split is coordinated by how the generators are defined. For a vector entirely in the $\{e_i\}$ frame we use a , for one entirely in the $\{f_i\}$ frame we use \check{a} ,

$$a = a_i e_i, \quad \check{a} = \check{a}_i f_i$$

¹² Or the more extreme view that or that spacetime is an illusion and the fields are all there is! We do not accept this view, as there is no way to ‘emerge’ spacetime from fields that have no space to begin with. One must at least postulate a Hilbert space as prior *meta*-physics.

For the *internal space* (the topological geon geometry) there is a distinguished unit imaginary, denoted J , defined by,

$$J = e_1 f_1 + e_2 f_2 + e_3 f_3.$$

There are nine elementary bivectors, defined to avoid duplicates up to a \pm sign for $i < j$,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{ij} &= e_i e_j - f_i f_j \\ F_{ij} &= e_i f_j + e_j f_i \\ J_i &= e_i f_i, \quad \text{no sum.} \end{aligned}$$

These definitions form the initial development of the symmetry generators, for the adjoint representation (bosons) of the unitary groups.

A unitary group is distinguished by a commutator product (for a Lie bracket),

$$A \times B = \frac{1}{2}(AB - BA)$$

and to close the algebra the generators of the group are precisely the bivectors, B , satisfying $B \times J = 0$.

If we were to continue in this manner with Cl_6 we can get one generation of Standard Model fermions, using Lasenby’s approach for example, or Stoica. This would leave the model with anomalies, making it an unphysical theory. According to standard Tree level QFT calculations we need three generations of LR-symmetric SM fermions and 36 dimension zero scalars to eliminate the trace, Weyl and vacuum anomalies [15].

IV. SYMMETRY, MASS AND GENERATIONS

We are not going to show how mass ratios can be computed here, these are more overarching remarks.

A number of threads get woven in our T4G picture, once we associate a quantization of this classical spacetime geometry with imposing a \mathbb{C} -structure. Real spacetime is not a complex structure, but contains classically the holomorphic structures inherited from the bivector subalgebras. The question which draws some threads together is what could the minimal additional \mathbb{C} -structure be arising from in real spacetimes?

A first consideration is that while it is certainly possible to find the Standard Model Algebra (SMA) in a high enough dimension Clifford Algebra, it can be hard to get the charges assigned consistently, and eliminating unobserved ‘particles’ (aka transformation instructions in in our lexicon) may then require imposition of seemingly *ad hoc* superselection rules, it is desirable too seek a minimal Clifford Algebra.

To our present knowledge it appears a complexification of some Cl_n is such a minimal approach. However, in T4G theory we want real spacetime geometry. We can turn this from a bug into a feature by providing a real geometric meaning for the complexification.

To do so, one simply demands real spacetime geometry, and then reverse engineers (so-to-speak) to find what real geometry is generating the need for \mathbb{C} -structure. There may be some sophisticated way to go about this, but a most naïve way is to recognize that the real \mathcal{Cl} models are classical models for the particle physics. The quantization is then supposed to be what demands the additional \mathbb{C} -structure.

In T4G this is not just a trick, it is necessary because the only way we can get a quantum theory out of T4G is to presume Planck scale wormhole topology. If we do not account for such topology, we would be forced outside of real spacetime geometry into abstractions (like Calabi-Yau strings or fibre bundles — but note that even those models still require quantization!). T4G theory is highly parsimonious in that no additional structure is needed for quantization, and so the complexification is completely explained by real spacetime geometry in 4D.

We mention just one more thread to tie in here (there are others we will not touch upon) which is that the picture of QM that T4G inherits is the indivisible stochastic dynamics theory of Barandes [35], which we dub ISQM, since it is a natural fit. Many others have argued that \mathbb{C} -structure is necessary for orthodox QM, without any specific SMA symmetry considerations. Hence we inherit those *as well*, because ISQM is completely orthodox QM compatible, via Barandes’ Stochastic–Quantum correspondence [16].

The thread tied in here is that a \mathbb{C} -structure is to be associated with a quantization of the SMA. But in T4G theory the SMA is a purely stochastic theory, given the underlying structure of the Dirac–Hestenes spinor which we covered in §II.C. The spinor is nothing but a transformation instruction, and the spacetime dependence in the $\sqrt{\rho}$ factor is a fundamentally statistical variable. Note only is this the most parsimonious interpretation of the spinor, but it perfectly conforms with Barandes’ framework.

The Dirac–Hestenes spinor is however purely classical. To quantize this classical under-pinning of the SMA we probably should complexify first, rather than lift up to a higher dimensional real \mathcal{Cl} . Why? Because we seek a minimal model. If it later proves necessary to raise the dimensions, we can then search for a 4D interpretation again by trying to reverse engineer to find a SMA topology in 4D.¹³

It is perhaps best left to later papers to discuss this in more detail, but the result of synthesizing the stochastic theory with the need to quantize the classical SMA, but also within 4D spacetime context, is to associate the \mathbb{C} phase with wormhole oscillations, or in the stochastic frame with duality transforms — the stochastic theory

being mostly ‘blind’ to real physical geometry. This is a three-way synthesis, so super-parsimonious.

Having a real 4D spacetime account means we should be able to find explanations for the Yukawa mass matrices, and a Higgs mechanism.

Lastly for this section, note that the statistical theory is also a theory of symmetry. All probability frameworks are, because they presume symmetry among equiprobable events. But from our scan of the literature, admittedly not comprehensive, few physicists seem to associate the spinor theories with fundamentally stochastic dynamics, more often the thought never arises, but also sometimes the ideology is that this *is* the “real stuff” (one might say a statistical ontology) which to our way of thinking is nonsensical.

In summary, the key to the synthesis is to recognize the spinor theory as fundamentally a stochastic description of events, and then complexification as an algebraic way to impose indivisible stochastic dynamics which yields the quantum theory (ISQM). This so far is standard. T4G adds a real geometric account for the complexification (read: quantization) which is the wormhole topology, which is the real cause of the indivisible stochastic dynamics.

What we presently lack in T4G theory is a good translation from the abstract complex unitary transforms to the wormhole topology. We conjecture there must exist a correspondence.

IV.A. A Realization in \mathcal{Cl}_4

The minimal model we can possibly find, one that uses the complexification as an ansatz, is complexified Space-time Algebra \mathcal{Cl}_4 . We can, since we are imposing T4G principles, take the \mathbb{C} -structure to be a *consequence* of the wormhole topology — but of course not directly, it is indirect via the correspondence of real spacetime cobordism structure to the indivisible (non-Markov) stochastic dynamics.

This model was worked out by Jason Blood.[49] We mention it in passing because it would have been nice to see from bare T4G theory that there was a need for complexification of the STA ($\mathcal{Cl}_{3,1}$) if a topological 4-geon based Clifford algebra for the Standard Model was to be desired. Unfortunately we were unable to make this conceptual leap in time! Too many threads came together all at once, which we will remark upon again at the end of the conclusions §VII.B.

IV.B. Electroweak Sector

In the STA the algebra for the electroweak interactions (see [50]) is covered by the spacetime pseudoscalar I for phase rotations, and the three Pauli matrices for $\mathfrak{su}(2)$,

$$\{I\sigma_1, I\sigma_2, I\sigma_3, I = e_0e_1e_2e_3.\}$$

¹³ We would like to reiterate that we are *not* arguing String Theory is wrong, we are only trying to find a 4D spacetime alternative, hence excluding String Theories from consideration by policy design.

The generators $I\sigma_k$ are all space bivectors, hence generators of rotations. In the STA the gauge transform act on the right of ψ , and Lorentz rotations from the left. This is enforced by the structure of Dirac theory. Why this is so will be explained in §-V.A.2.

Most of this is classical geometry. The quantum theory developed from this STA is an additional structure, which is imposed by the theory of measurements in our framework.

IV.C. Strong (color) Sector

The paper by Hestenes [50], and the paper by Lasenby [7] discuss the natural $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ subalgebras of 4D spacetime. We will not review them because there are known unresolved issues with chirality (lack thereof) and triality (they have only one generation). By connecting with Garrett Lisi’s CPTt work, the STA group could perhaps find a triality automorphism, but if so it would make our T4G approach seem strangely superfluous.

In our current estimation they would also not be able to account for quantum entanglement in any but a purely *ad hoc* fashion, which is another reason for skipping a review of their results. Entanglement is simple enough to incorporate once superpositions of states are admitted, but that is exactly what we mean by *ad hoc*. T4G theory has entanglement-by-design, or one could say that entanglement is unavoidable in T4G theory.

V. EXPLORING CA MODELS

Besides the previous section discussions, have no other compelling clues about what CA so-to-speak “Nature uses.” But the general idea of research for T4G could be illustrated using Cl_6 as a first example. We believe Cl_6 cannot accommodate three fermion families, and so is only a toy model. We can nevertheless be clear about the purpose of toy models before we begin.

First off, the purpose is *not* to generate publications! The purpose is to gain familiarity with algebra that most physicists are thoroughly unfamiliar with. But we have one more specific purpose.

The main purpose is to bring our research into alignment with our whole philosophy that the wavefunctions are not particle representations, but rather they are the transformation instructions that one needs in order to go *from* laboratory frame *to* comoving frames of the elementary particle. This view is an underappreciated subculture within the geometric algebra community.

It gains even great hold on our theoretical efforts because of the background T4G ideas. At present T4GT does not provide explicit topological structures for the elementary particles. Nor do experiments. For all its good, String Theory does not provide many clues either. What we are then faced with is the reverse engineering task we mentioned before.

This is why exploring toy models might be of some practical use. Just as one studies triangles to appreciate the symmetries of say tetrahedra, we consider exploring the lower dimensional CA’s as instructive for how the transformations we call ψ in quantum theory might be found in algebra. If the geometry is clear, then this might lead to some thoughts on the algebraic topology of the Standard Model, and then finally, one might hope, to the spacetime topology itself, should T4G theory be a good theory for describing elementary particle physics.

V.1. A Cl_6 Example

We are claiming the Standard Model is not modelling ER=EPR wormholes completely, only some basic algebraic relations are getting modelled. In the T4G theory we will be using a Cl_6 subalgebra of Cl_8 algebra for the $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ sector, which has six basis vectors $\{\vec{e}_i, \vec{f}_i\}$. The $\mathfrak{u}(3)$ generators are,

$$E_{ij} = e_i e_j - f_i f_j, \quad F_{ij} = e_i f_j - f_j e_i, \quad J_i = e_i f_i.$$

We will interpret this Clifford structure as composed from frame vectors (3-biens) at each wormhole end in a topological 4-geon. Because the set $\{e_i\}$ is at a different end of the wormhole to the set $\{f_i\}$, the ‘mixed’ bivectors F_{ij} and J_i in the algebra for $\mathfrak{u}(3)$ no longer have the standard geometrical meaning of an oriented area for a rotation plane, although one may still conceive of the bivectors in the abstract in such terms if desired. What this abstraction means in spacetime terms is not clear to us, but following the gauge field theory history one would wave ones hands and proclaim these bivectors for generators of ‘internal rotations’ — meaning inside the abstract fibre bundle.

This is unacceptable to us of course, we prefer to look for a smooth topological cobordism interpretation of these ‘internal’ rotations.

V.A. Complexified Cl_8 Mother Algebra

This is the key section of this paper. In private communications [49], Jason Blood of Arizona State University suggested we should be using a complexified Clifford algebra for analyticity. This is ostensibly to avoid unwanted unphysical rotations which would otherwise be allowed if we used the \mathbb{R} representations.

Jason’s other innovation [51] was to treat the $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ on the same footing as the Lorentz rotations, so in Clifford algebra thus acting-from-the-left. This seems a small adjustment, but is algebraically a cleaner treatment which differs from the Hestenes–Lasenby–Doran Cambridge school. (Jason is at Hestenes’ alma mater, but we are unaware of any strong connection to Hestenes, the latter being more firmly in the 4D STA camp.)

An additional advantage of Jason’s approach is that the isomorphisms for complexified Clifford Cl_n are $Cl_n \otimes$

$\mathcal{Cl}_{0,2}$, in other words, a tensor structure is implied if we wish to have the aforementioned nice analyticity. This is an unexpected bonus feature, as it were, for the topological 4-geon theory, because we would otherwise need to motivate a tensor structure for the wormhole topology. Using Blood's framework the \mathcal{Cl}_8 is "doing this" naturally for us.

There is additional oblique support for this idea that $\mathcal{Cl}_{0,2}$ structure is algebraic is an algebraic shadow so-to-speak of spacetime wormholes, coming from PT symmetric Hamiltonian theory [52] where switching between spin \uparrow and spin \downarrow goes via a wormhole-like effect¹⁴.

The only embarrassment at present is that we seem to get a doubling of the Standard Model. This is really the main result we wish to report upon, and encourage others to look for bugs or fixes, or explain as natural the structure we have found. Jason is pursuing a fibre bundle ontology, and so may not be so concerned, although we feel in that ontology it should be more worrisome, since there is no natural explanation.

In T4G ontology we have at-hand a natural explanation, because the Standard Model should look the same for both ends of the 4-geon wormholes. In other words, an algebraic doubling of the Standard Model would not be unexpected. To be sure, it is perhaps still undesirable, but the more optimistic view is that it is a blessing in the disguise or a redundancy. T4G done-well might demand this redundancy. At this stage of research we are agnostic.

We will now outline the model and present a Standard Model tableau.

V.A.1. Witt Basis and Primitive Idempotents

In our software checks we worked with a $(- - - +)$ signature for two copies of spacetime. This is just to note in case replication finds sign differences (the signature is irrelevant for any complexified Clifford algebra).

We think of the parent \mathcal{Cl}_8 as two copies of $\mathcal{Cl}_{1,3}$, but with no explicit tensor product. We are regarding the complex phase as the tensor structure (the 'wormhole', so-to-speak). With the orthonormal basis thus $\{e_\mu, f_\mu\}$, we can write down a first Witt basis (the algebra for raising and lowering operators)

$$\begin{aligned} q_0 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_4 - e_3), & Q_0 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_4 + e_3) \\ q_1 &= (-e_1 - ie_2), & Q_1 &= (e_1 - ie_2) \\ q_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_4 - f_3), & Q_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_4 + f_3) \\ q_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(-f_1 - if_2), & Q_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_1 - if_2). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

(Students may be encouraged to play with alternative representations.)

NB: In most treatments our Q_i will be written q_i^\dagger , for the raising property as number operators acting on the vacuum primitive idempotents. However, we view and review our work mainly in L^AT_EX and so it is cleaner to use capital letters for the q^\dagger and the later alternate Witt bases, a^\dagger and b^\dagger .

From the defining properties for a Witt basis,

$$\{q_i, q_j\} = 0, \quad \{q_i^\dagger, q_j^\dagger\} = 0, \quad \{q_i, q_j^\dagger\} = \delta_{ij}$$

we could also recover the orthonormal basis using the inverse to the above relations.

A first set of 16 primitive idempotents can now be formed, it is easy to check these are idempotents v_a , $a \in 1, \dots, 16$, and that the Witt basis elements act like number operators on each of these vacua, the first ... and after some suitable combinatorial permutations of basis elements, the last are,

$$\begin{aligned} v_1 &= q_0 Q_0 q_1 Q_1 q_2 Q_2 q_3 Q_3, \\ &\dots \\ v_{16} &= Q_0 q_0 Q_1 q_1 Q_2 q_2 Q_3 q_3. \end{aligned}$$

Here Clifford multiplication is implied, so we are getting mixed grade multivectors from hereon, in general.

Let us repeat, and to appease spacetime algebra enthusiasts, the "uninterpreted" unit imaginary i here, is no longer uninterpreted, it represents real spacetime structure, a phase rotation allowed along the wormhole which we regard as existing internal to all 4-geon elementary p[articles]. It is necessarily minimal geometry because the 4-geon wormhole is not a classical GR wormhole, it is Planck scale, i.e., minimal, and classically non-traversable.

It is easy to now check that we recover a Lorentzian 4D spacetime local tetrad from an inverse to the Witt basis definition,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_0 &= Q_0 + q_0, \\ \gamma_1 &= Q_1 - q_1, \\ \gamma_2 &= i(Q_1 + q_1), \\ \gamma_3 &= Q_0 - q_0, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

We will use these later to define chiral and spin- z projection operators, which will be multivectors in the \mathcal{Cl}_8 .

V.A.2. Spinor Ideals and Left/Right Action

Left Ideals are defined by all the elementary multivectors taken from the even subalgebra which do not annihilate their vacuum. So there is one left Ideal for each of the above 16 primitive idempotents. These elements will have coefficients of course, which you may insert to compare with say matrix representations of Weyl spinors (the Weyl basis is appropriate for extracting chiral spinor

¹⁴ Here though, in Carl Bender's work, the wormhole is in Hilbert space, rather than spacetime, hence in T4G parlance really it is a transformation instruction shadow of a real spacetime wormhole connection.

components). But we can avoid appeal to matrix representation entirely if we wish.

For $SU(2)$ action this model permits us action from-the-left. This is highly significant. It places the $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ isospace rotations on a similar footing to the Lorentz rotations, which also act on-the-left. Let us first describe how this is accomplished in $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$, and then why in the Clifford algebra the distinctions between left-action and right-action matter.

Moreover, this allowance to use $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ action from-the-left is a pot of departure from both the STA ($C\ell_{3,1}$) models [7, 50] which lack chirality and triality, and the more traditional $C\ell_8$ models of Gresnigt *et al* [12].

It is easy to see how left-acting $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ rotations are allowed, the issue is, as we will see shortly, we cannot mix the Lorentz rotations with the internal gauge rotations. How can we avoid the mixing? The answer is that in $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ we can place all of $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ in the (23) Witt sector. Recall the definitions (3), or more clearly note the inverted relations for the spacetime orthonormal basis (4). The Minkowski frame $\{\gamma_\mu\}$ are defined in terms of only the set $\{q_0^{(\dagger)}, q_1^{(\dagger)}\}$, that is, the Witt (01) sector.

This means if we use the bivector generators from $\{q_2^{(\dagger)}, q_3^{(\dagger)}\}$ for $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ rotations then they can act on-the-left without mixing with the Lorentz rotations, which are generated by $\{q_0^{(\dagger)}, q_1^{(\dagger)}\}$.

The $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ rotation however are formed from Witt generators $\{q_1^{(\dagger)}, q_2^{(\dagger)}, q_3^{(\dagger)}\}$, or the (123) Witt sector, and so would mix with the Lorentz rotations, and so must act from-the-right. This is perhaps not yet a physically motivated aspect of Jason Blood's $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ algebra, but it is "mathematically natural" and to the extent the geometric algebra shadows real spacetime geometry and topology, one can put a philosophical hat on and claim it is pretty good physical motivation, or at least pre-physical (amounting to a type of spacetime realism).

Let us now back up a step and explain why in the Clifford algebra formulations of quantum mechanics this left-action versus right-action distinction is important, and obscured in the orthodox matrix algebra treatments.

Why do Lorentz rotors act on the left of ψ ? ... and why do Unitary transforms act on the Right? To make this explicit, we are saying:

$$\text{Lorentz transform: } \psi \longrightarrow \psi' = L\psi$$

$$\text{Unitary transform: } \psi \longrightarrow \psi' = \psi R$$

And why are there only these two options *physically*?

First of all, we should note that in Clifford algebra the left/right distinction matters since the outer products are antisymmetric,

$$a \wedge b = -b \wedge a$$

and this is simply basic respect for orientation! This is what it all boils down to. The bivectors that represent planes of rotation, have a handedness (in any spacetime

dimension). That said, this does not inform us about why the Lorentz action *has to be* different to the Unitary action.

The symmetry operators are characterized as exponentials of generators. For the boosts and unitary transforms the generators are slightly different.

- Lorentz: the generators are spacetime bivectors $\gamma_k \gamma_0$. Using the spacetime frame. Here γ_0 or is the observer's laboratory time direction.
- Unitary: the generators are formed from the elementary 4-geons' local frame field $\{e_\mu\}$, a comoving frame, with the particle, so the e_0 is always oriented in the direction of the particle current. In a naïve model, $\mathfrak{u}(1)$ and $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ generators are $\{I, \sigma_k\}$.

These are related because the STA spinor itself is composed of $C\ell_{3,1}^+$ subalgebra elements (at least the Dirac, Weyl and Majorana spinors are). So also can the Twistors and Octonions, if you prefer to work with those algebras.

To address:

“... we act on the right of ψ because these are really for gauging the covariant derivative ...”

it might be useful to recall what exactly the gauge rotations are doing in the first place. They arise from symmetries of the Lagrangian for the elementary particles. They are called “internal” symmetries because they do nothing to the laboratory frame, but do permute or mix or ‘phase rotate’ the elementary particle states. The idea these symmetries refer to transforms among elementary particles arises from the modelling choice we have to take what it *means* to be an elementary particle is that you transform according to the irreducible representations of the symmetries of Nature. What are these symmetries? Well, we have to empirically discover them from physical observable invariants (like charge, rest mass, lepton number, baryon numbers, ‘color’ and so forth).

This is less mysterious than beginners might imagine. The whole idea of a “particle” is here based upon invariants. That implies stability, or in some case orbits (like the fermion families) of symmetry transforms.

(To follow particle physics conventions I will use ∇ below for the spacetime vector derivative, although normally I'd use \square .)

Normally gauge theory is taught by starting with some global symmetry. Under which the spinors transform:

$$\psi \longrightarrow \psi' = \psi R$$

For our present purposes all we need is that the transform is some rotor, R . Specific cases, like electromagnetism, weak, and strong gauges, can be dealt with in the appropriate way. I want to keep this aside exposition generic.

The spacetime derivative terms in the Lagrangian therefore undergo:

$$\nabla \psi \longrightarrow \nabla(\psi R) = \nabla \psi R + \psi \nabla R$$

If R has no position dependence the second term vanishes, and so the EOM or Lagrangian is invariant. The symmetry was without physical consequence. (Like a global rotation.) A “force” arises when the symmetry is promoted to a local symmetry, meaning $R = R(x)$. Now the gradient term makes the EOM not respect the symmetry. To recover local symmetry we need to use a covariant derivative. We attempt to construct one:

$$D\psi = \nabla\psi + \psi A(x)$$

To cancel the ∇R term in the EOM we need A to transform like,

$$A \longrightarrow A' = \tilde{R}AR - \tilde{R}\nabla R$$

This ensures the EOM will remain invariant,

$$\begin{aligned} (D\psi)' &= \nabla\psi R + \psi\nabla R + \psi R(\tilde{R}AR - \tilde{R}\nabla R) \\ &= \nabla\psi R + \psi\nabla R + \psi AR - \psi\nabla R \\ &= (\nabla\psi + A\psi)' \end{aligned}$$

as required.

From here the development goes on to find a field quantity related to A which is physical. The gauge field A is non-physical because it is frame-dependent. But this is not our task today. Today all we want to examine is the Clifford structure: why the gauge rotation has to act **on the right**.

Note: the above demo is not coordinate free, since we are using some frame for ∇ , and the “proper” way to use the Clifford Algebra is to do all of this coordinate free, which can be done, but is not our present task.

What if R was on the Left?

Towards some contradictions, suppose we now attempt to let this act on the left, i.e.,

$$\psi(x) \mapsto R(x)\psi(x)$$

What could go wrong? I think there are three problems we can highlight.

Problem 1. The Dirac Equation Transformation Fails. We start with the (free) STA Dirac equation:

$$\nabla\psi I\sigma_3 = m\psi\gamma_0$$

Let’s apply the transformation $\psi \mapsto R(x)\psi$. Then, the left-hand side becomes:

$$\nabla(R\psi)I\sigma_3 = (\nabla R)\psi I\sigma_3 + R(\nabla\psi)I\sigma_3$$

The right-hand side becomes:

$$mR\psi\gamma_0$$

So we get a new unwanted first term here:

$$(\nabla R)\psi I\sigma_3$$

But now *unlike before* this term does *not* vanish unless $R = \text{const}$, i.e. unless the transformation is global.

By contrast, if R acted *on the right*, we could define a gauge field $A(x)$ as above, to absorb the derivative of $R(x)$, via the usual gauge transformation:

$$A' = \tilde{R}AR - (\nabla R)\tilde{R}$$

which ensured the covariant derivative transforms covariantly.

But when R acts *on-the-left*, there’s no consistent way to fix that unwanted derivative term using a right-acting gauge field. The correction term from ∇R sits on the wrong side of ψ , so we can’t absorb it by modifying A .

This may seem almost facile, but really it is deep. You cannot just mess around with the order of geometric products. On paper we are representing orientation and more fundamentally mirror reflections (as I will discuss below) and we cannot just move symbols around in Clifford algebra. The same is true in matrix algebra, but in the Clifford algebra we have a clear geometric reason for the commutative and anticommutative structure. It all starts from the mirror reflections.

Result: There’s no natural way to define a gauge field A that transforms consistently with a left-acting $R(x)$. The attempt to write an algebraically consistent covariant derivative fails.

Problem 2. The Observable Currents Become Inconsistent. Take a physical observable like the Dirac current:

$$J = \psi\gamma_\mu\tilde{\psi}$$

Under $\psi \rightarrow R\psi$, we have,

$$J \mapsto R\psi\gamma_\mu\tilde{\psi}\tilde{R} = RJ\tilde{R}$$

That is: the internal phase rotation $R = e^{\alpha(x)I}$ now rotates spacetime vectors like J , which it should not do. It should only be rotating the spinor frame vectors γ_μ .

But for EM since I commutes with all spacetime vectors (because it’s a pseudoscalar), so this doesn’t *appear* to cause problems at first glance for EM. However — the real problem shows up when you go to non-abelian gauge group. For instance, $SU(2)$ or $SU(3)$ transformations do not commute with spacetime vectors or bivectors.

Thus, if gauge rotors act on the left, they interfere with the Lorentz structure of observables like $\psi\gamma_\mu\tilde{\psi}$, leading to incorrect transformations of currents and coupling terms.

Put another way, in a closed algebra left-acting gauge rotors contaminate the spacetime frame structure.

Problem 3. Gauge Fields Cannot Be Consistently Coupled on the Left. If we try to define a covariant derivative:

$$D\psi = \nabla\psi + A\psi$$

Then we need to use the overdot differential notation (for starters a warning sign), but let’s try, supposing,

$$A \rightarrow A' = RA\tilde{R} - (\nabla R)\tilde{R}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(D\psi)' &= (\nabla R)\psi + \dot{\nabla}R\dot{\psi} + A'R\psi \\
&= (\nabla R)\psi + \dot{\nabla}R\dot{\psi} + RA\psi - (\nabla R)\psi \\
&= \dot{\nabla}R\dot{\psi} + RA\psi \\
&\neq (\nabla\psi + A\psi)'
\end{aligned}$$

this appears to be an obstacle to getting a covariant derivative, we cannot just pull R out to the left here. We seem to require non-commutative control over the ordering between ∇ , R , and ψ , which is far less tractable than the clean right-action version.

Another way I like to think of this stuff is in terms of maps and their adjoints. This is related because in Clifford algebra the adjoint map is a type of left-to-right relation. Given any linear function f , the adjoint denoted \bar{f} is defined by,

$$a \cdot f(b) = \bar{f}(a) \cdot a$$

We can have this nice algebraic definition in Clifford algebra because the dual space spanned by $\{e^i\}$ can be expressed in terms of geometric products in the base space $\{e_i\}$. It is a nice homework exercise to get students to show the dual space does satisfy the requirements,

$$e^i \cdot e_j = \delta_j^i$$

One can take that relation as the definition and then construct a dual basis from,

$$e^j = (-1)^{j-1} e_1 \wedge e_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \check{e}_j \wedge \dots \wedge e_n E_n^{-1}$$

where $E_n = e_1 e_2 \dots e_n$ is the unit pseudoscalar for the vector space, assuming here we've chosen an orthonormal base $\{e_i\}$.

Back in the Spacetime Algebra, the algebra design that leads to our left-action versus right-action distinction really traces all the way back to how we write mirror reflections. First we note the structure for the rotations is,

$$v \longrightarrow v' = \tilde{R}vR$$

but this traces back to the mirror reflection across a plane, specified by a unit normal, \vec{n} say, expressed by,

$$v \longrightarrow -nvn$$

so that a general rotation being a composite of two reflections is specified by a rotor $R = mn$,

$$v \longrightarrow -n(-mvm)n = nmvmn = \tilde{R}vR.$$

Which works in any space dimension because a pair of unit vectors defines a unique plane of rotation.

Ultimately of course this is just a choice of how we scribble down symbols on paper. The deep explanation is really category theoretic, or functorial. We really should use diagrammatic notation I feel, to reveal the structure here in the Clifford algebra. "Act on the right" means something categorically.

To get a further handle on it we should turn to the other side, the left-hand side, which is "where we act" with Lorentz rotors. Notice the spatial metaphor! The algebra order relations are telling us something about spacetime topology and symmetry.

Can we now explain *why* the Lorentz rotor acts on the left? The basic reason is that in the STA spinors are *themselves* active frame-rotors.

What this means is that if you think of a vector x , it is transformed under a Lorentz rotation as:

$$x \mapsto \tilde{L}xL$$

but if ψ is a rotor encoding the observer's frame, then the physical observables are things like:

$$\mathcal{O}(x) = \tilde{\psi}x\psi$$

So to rotate the **frame**, you act **on** ψ . To rotate the frame, not the object or physical observable in the frame, you have to act as such:

$$\psi \mapsto L\psi$$

Why? Because then (by algebraic design or necessity),

$$\mathcal{O}(x) \mapsto (L\psi) \tilde{\ } x(L\psi) = \tilde{L}(\tilde{\psi}x\psi)L$$

That is, the entire transformed observable transforms correctly under Lorentz symmetry. It would not otherwise.

So, left action of L rotates the **frame rotor**. In contrast, acting on x by conjugation transforms the **physical vector**. This is why the spinor ψ itself must transform by left multiplication: it's the rotor defining the frame.

This is not arbitrary: it's the defining property of spinors as frame objects in STA.

Consider the Wrong Way: Let's now carefully explain why acting on the right instead of the left leads to the wrong physical transformation. Consider again what the spinor is really doing. In STA a spinor ψ is not a mysterious complex column vector. Instead, it is a scaled rotor — a multivector that rotates and boosts vectors.

This means if you take a vector X (like a position or velocity), and transform it via:

$$X' = \tilde{\psi}X\psi$$

then this sandwich product rotates and/or boosts the vector x into a new vector x' . It is how we compute the Observable associated with the multivector x . Which is why I would prefer notation,

$$\mathcal{O}(X) = \tilde{\psi}X\psi$$

The spinor ψ here encodes a local frame — a kind of observer's coordinate axes, only here "the observer" really is the elementary particle (ignoring the stochastic aspects of QM for now).

Now what happens when we apply a Lorentz rotation?

Case 1: Left multiplication by Lorentz rotor L . This is the correct transformation of the spinor:

$$\psi \mapsto L\psi$$

Then the transformed observable is:

$$\mathcal{O}(X') = \tilde{\psi}X\psi \mapsto (L\psi) \tilde{X}(L\psi) = \tilde{L}(\tilde{\psi}X\psi)L$$

which is exactly what we want: the vector $\mathcal{O}(X) = \psi X \tilde{\psi}$ gets Lorentz transformed to:

$$\mathcal{O}(X') \mapsto \tilde{L}\mathcal{O}(X)L.$$

That is, the physical observable $\mathcal{O}(x')$ is Lorentz rotated.

Case 2: Right multiplication by Lorentz rotor L

Suppose instead we try:

$$\psi \mapsto \psi L$$

Then the transformed observable becomes:

$$\mathcal{O}(X) = \tilde{\psi}X\psi \mapsto (\psi L) \tilde{X}(\psi L) = \tilde{\psi}(\tilde{L}X L)\psi$$

This means we have first Lorentz-transformed the multi-vector X , then rotated the result via $\tilde{\psi}X\psi$.

But that's backwards! We'd have applied the Lorentz rotation to the object, not to the observer's frame. This would mean the *vector in the world* got rotated independently, *before* we measure it in our rotated frame. This is not relativistically correct!

This completes our pedagogical review of left-action versus right-action. In the matrix formulation of QM these distinctions are more-or-less "put in by hand" using extra matrix indices, with little motivation other than "it has to be made to work." However, the Clifford sandwich product is hiding in plain sight in Dirac's QM, in the bracket.

One last note: the fact the Witt basis vectors can annihilate the alternative vacuum (primitive idempotents) only one-sided makes this left/right action distinction manifest, q.v.,

$$\begin{aligned} q_1(\dots q_1 Q_1 \dots) &\mapsto 0, \\ (\dots q_1 Q_1 \dots)q_1 &\mapsto \dots q_1(1 - q_1 Q_1) \dots \mapsto -(\dots q_1 \dots) \end{aligned}$$

which again is obscured by mere fiat diktat so-to-speak in matrix QM.

* * *

We can now immediately label a few of the elementary fermions in some of the left Ideals. For example, the spinor ideal for the first vacuum, v_1 , is,

$$\psi_1 \sim \underbrace{\underbrace{(1 + Q_0 Q_1)}_R + \underbrace{(Q_0 + Q_1) Q_2}_L}_{\nu} + \underbrace{\underbrace{(Q_0 + Q_1) Q_3}_L + \underbrace{(1 + Q_0 Q_1) Q_2 Q_3}_R}_e \quad (5)$$

The \sim relation here indicates we have suppressed all the scalar coefficients for readability. It is obviously not a direct proportionality, it is a spinor with all scalar coefficients set to = 1, so is un-normalized, but since normalization does not bother our charge and projection operator eigenvalue identifications this will not bother us.

Also, the above spinor is not the Ideal, the full left ideal is that spinor multiplied on the right by v_1 .

Using the exact same permutation of the set of $\{q_i, Q_i\}$ used to obtain each vacua v_a , one may obtain the left spinor ideal for that corresponding vacuum. We will thus not bother writing down the full list.

However, we do need to check those chirality and charge assignments. Notice in each bracketed pair of chiral fermions there is allowance for a spin- \uparrow and spin- \downarrow as well, which we will later tabulate on page 22.

It is possible to code these ideals and vacua in a standard Clifford algebra software package. Most such software will generate an orthonormal basis, and print-out representations will thus be in terms of the orthonormal basis 1-vectors. The Witt basis is much easier to

manipulate on pen & paper due to the fermionic (grassmann) algebra, but for checking the $\mathfrak{u}(3)$ subalgebra the orthonormal basis is handy, we find if we define bivector generators as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{ij} &= e_i e_j + f_i f_j, & F_{ij} &= e_i f_j + e_j f_i \\ J_i &= e_i f_i, & \text{no summation,} \end{aligned}$$

and then define Gell-Mann λ_i $i = 1 \dots 8$,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1 &= \frac{1}{2} F_{12}, & \lambda_2 &= \frac{1}{2} E_{12}, \\ \lambda_3 &= \frac{1}{2} (J_1 - J_2), & \lambda_4 &= \frac{1}{2} F_{13}, \\ \lambda_5 &= \frac{1}{2} E_{13}, & \lambda_6 &= \frac{1}{2} F_{23}, \\ \lambda_7 &= \frac{1}{2} E_{23}, & \lambda_8 &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{6} (J_1 + J_2 - 2J_3) \end{aligned}$$

then the usual $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ structure constants are correct.

V.A.3. Spinor Ideal Charges

The Cartan generators are λ_3 and λ_8 . We thus use these to compute the $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ charge assignments (quark

colors). With appropriate software this is easy to automate, we just code up a list of the possible weights, $w_k^{(3)}, w_k^{(8)}$, then run a loop over k , and the elementary components of the spinor ideals, ψ , checking,

$$\psi\lambda_3 - w_k^{(3)}\psi \equiv 0, \quad \psi\lambda_8 - w_k^{(8)}\psi \equiv 0.$$

We then find the each vacua v_a , $a = 1, \dots, 16$ is monocolored, either (r, g, b) or anti-colored $(\bar{r}, \bar{g}, \bar{b})$.

For chirality we found a hint that the complex structure is as theorized elsewhere, practically “essential” for chiral fermions, although we are presently unsure why this is the case for any intrinsic physical spacetime reason. It is one of those typical “the algebra says so” aspects for the time being. In any case, this is all due to the simple fact the correct chiral assignments are computed by the projectors,

$$P_R = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \Gamma_5) \\ P_L = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \Gamma_5)$$

where $\Gamma_5 = iI$, and $I = \gamma_0\gamma_1\gamma_2\gamma_3$ is the spacetime pseudoscalar.

Is it the case that chiral fermion models are consequences of a demand for analyticity in the spinor transformations?

In any case, these two projectors explain how we arrived at the L and R labels for the example spinor above in (5).

Similarly we can define spin- z projectors, without needing matrix algebra, These are,

$$P_\uparrow = \frac{1}{2}(1 + 2S_z) \\ P_\downarrow = \frac{1}{2}(1 - 2S_z)$$

where the spin- z observable is,

$$S_z = \frac{1}{2}i\gamma_1\gamma_2$$

So that any student can follow along, we can give an example for checking the chirality of a candidate left-neutrino, ν_L . Guessing from the v_1 ideal that this might be,

$$\nu_L = (Q_0Q_2 + Q_1Q_2)v_1$$

we simply check $P_L\nu_L - \nu_L \stackrel{?}{=} 0$. Similarly the spinor with component $\nu_R = (1 + Q_0Q_1)$ satisfies $P_R\nu_R - \nu_R \stackrel{?}{=} 0$.

As a further example, each of these neutrinos has a spin- \uparrow and spin- \downarrow component. In our Witt basis these are in fact the parts of the even subalgebra sums just given. The check is slightly trickier, we compute,,

$$\nu_R^\uparrow = P_\uparrow\nu_R' \\ S_z\nu_R'v_1 \stackrel{?}{=} \frac{1}{2}\nu_R'v_1$$

where $\nu_R' = 1 + Q_0Q_1$ is the elementary component (bivector). In other words we found we had to act on

the bivector component first, then post-multiply by the vacuum idempotent. It is not completely clear why this is the case, but it might be because we are working here in the Witt basis.

This just leaves the hypercharge assignments to do. Jason Blood [49] had figured out the appropriate Cartan diagonal operator for this (you could say it is the $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$ Casimir for the charges if you like).

We define a two-sided charge operator,

$$\mathcal{Q}(\psi) = \frac{1}{2}[q_3, Q_3]\psi - \frac{1}{6}\psi([q_1, Q_1] + [q_2, Q_2] + [q_3, Q_3]).$$

In the orthonormal basis we might write this in terms of deformations of the previously defined J_1, J_2, J_3 . But these new deformed \mathcal{J}_i are *not the same* as the $u(3)$ generators, J_i , from the orthonormal basis! The new \mathcal{J}_i here is used next in the definition of hypercharge, Y , are commutators from the Witt basis,

$$\mathcal{J}_i = [q_i, Q_i]$$

Thus more compactly,

$$\mathcal{Q}(\psi) = \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{J}_3\psi - \frac{1}{6}\psi(\mathcal{J}_1 + \mathcal{J}_2 + \mathcal{J}_3). \quad (6)$$

This also gives a check via hypercharge $Y = 2(\mathcal{Q} - T_3)$ if desired. Hypercharge would be,

$$Y(\psi) = \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{J}_3 + \mathcal{J}_2)\psi - \frac{1}{3}\psi(\mathcal{J}_1 + \mathcal{J}_2 + \mathcal{J}_3),$$

This was interesting to get different J_i generators, but we have not pursued the reason why. Although it might relate to the existence of automorphisms of $C\ell_8$, and thus might indicate triality. Whatever the case, we later found a triality automorphism via a simpler route.

V.A.4. The Main $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$ Tableaux

We now have everything we need to label the 16 spinor ideals. You may note each left Ideal has 8 spinor sub-components, and these will all get different labels. We compute electric charge so will see antiparticles. Thus we'd expect for a LR-symmetric Standard Model with no elementary Higgs [15] exactly 64 elementary fermions in one generation. But 16 left Ideals gives us 128. Great for just two fermion generations? We will come back to this question later, but suffice to note for now there is a triality symmetry in $C\ell_8$ so we do get three fermion generations, or 6! Take your pick. In the discussion (page 26) we will mention how six might reduce to three.

* * *

We believe the Tableaux in Table I is the same, or similar up to an automorphism on $C\ell_8$ as Jason Blood's model. Thus we believe all of Jason's work on coupling to gravity follows *a fortiori*.

Vacuum	Monomial	Type	Vacuum	Monomial	Type	Vacuum	Monomial	Type	Vacuum	Monomial	Type
v_1	1	ν_R^\uparrow	v_5	1	dg_R^\uparrow	v_9	1	$\bar{u}b_R^\uparrow$	v_{13}	1	$\bar{d}\bar{r}_R^\uparrow$
v_1	Q_0Q_1	ν_R^\downarrow	v_5	Q_0Q_1	dg_R^\downarrow	v_9	Q_0Q_1	$\bar{u}b_R^\downarrow$	v_{13}	Q_0Q_1	$\bar{d}\bar{r}_R^\downarrow$
v_1	Q_0Q_2	ν_L^\uparrow	v_5	Q_0Q_2	dg_L^\uparrow	v_9	Q_0Q_2	$\bar{u}b_L^\uparrow$	v_{13}	Q_0Q_2	$\bar{d}\bar{r}_L^\uparrow$
v_1	Q_1Q_2	ν_L^\downarrow	v_5	Q_1Q_2	dg_L^\downarrow	v_9	Q_1Q_2	$\bar{u}b_L^\downarrow$	v_{13}	Q_1Q_2	$\bar{d}\bar{r}_L^\downarrow$
v_1	Q_0Q_3	e_L^\downarrow	v_5	Q_0Q_3	$\bar{u}g_L^\downarrow$	v_9	Q_0Q_3	db_L^\uparrow	v_{13}	Q_0Q_3	$u\bar{r}_L^\uparrow$
v_1	Q_1Q_3	e_L^\uparrow	v_5	Q_1Q_3	$\bar{u}g_L^\uparrow$	v_9	Q_1Q_3	db_L^\downarrow	v_{13}	Q_1Q_3	$u\bar{r}_L^\downarrow$
v_1	Q_2Q_3	e_R^\downarrow	v_5	q_2Q_3	$\bar{u}g_R^\downarrow$	v_9	Q_2Q_3	db_R^\uparrow	v_{13}	q_2Q_3	$u\bar{r}_R^\uparrow$
v_1	$Q_0Q_1Q_2Q_3$	e_R^\uparrow	v_5	$Q_0Q_1q_2Q_3$	$\bar{u}g_R^\uparrow$	v_9	$Q_0Q_1Q_2q_3$	db_R^\downarrow	v_{13}	$Q_0Q_1q_2q_3$	$u\bar{r}_R^\downarrow$
v_2	1	ν_L^\uparrow	v_6	1	dg_L^\uparrow	v_{10}	1	$\bar{u}b_L^\uparrow$	v_{14}	1	$\bar{d}\bar{r}_L^\uparrow$
v_2	q_0Q_1	ν_L^\downarrow	v_6	q_0Q_1	dg_L^\downarrow	v_{10}	q_0Q_1	$\bar{u}b_L^\downarrow$	v_{14}	q_0Q_1	$\bar{d}\bar{r}_L^\downarrow$
v_2	q_0Q_2	ν_R^\uparrow	v_6	q_0Q_2	dg_R^\uparrow	v_{10}	q_0Q_2	$\bar{u}b_R^\uparrow$	v_{14}	q_0Q_2	$\bar{d}\bar{r}_R^\uparrow$
v_2	Q_1Q_2	ν_R^\downarrow	v_6	Q_1Q_2	dg_R^\downarrow	v_{10}	Q_1Q_2	$\bar{u}b_R^\downarrow$	v_{14}	Q_1Q_2	$\bar{d}\bar{r}_R^\downarrow$
v_2	q_0Q_3	e_R^\uparrow	v_6	q_0Q_3	$\bar{u}g_R^\uparrow$	v_{10}	q_0Q_3	db_R^\uparrow	v_{14}	q_0Q_3	$u\bar{r}_R^\uparrow$
v_2	Q_1Q_3	e_R^\downarrow	v_6	Q_1Q_3	$\bar{u}g_R^\downarrow$	v_{10}	Q_1Q_3	db_R^\downarrow	v_{14}	Q_1Q_3	$u\bar{r}_R^\downarrow$
v_2	Q_2Q_3	e_L^\downarrow	v_6	q_2Q_3	$\bar{u}g_L^\downarrow$	v_{10}	Q_2Q_3	db_L^\uparrow	v_{14}	q_2Q_3	$u\bar{r}_L^\uparrow$
v_2	$q_0Q_1Q_2Q_3$	e_L^\uparrow	v_6	$q_0Q_1q_2Q_3$	$\bar{u}g_L^\uparrow$	v_{10}	$q_0Q_1Q_2q_3$	db_L^\downarrow	v_{14}	$q_0Q_1q_2q_3$	$u\bar{r}_L^\downarrow$
v_3	1	dr_L^\downarrow	v_7	1	$u\bar{b}_L^\downarrow$	v_{11}	1	$\bar{d}\bar{g}_L^\downarrow$	v_{15}	1	\bar{v}_L^\downarrow
v_3	Q_0q_1	dr_L^\uparrow	v_7	Q_0q_1	$u\bar{b}_L^\uparrow$	v_{11}	Q_0q_1	$\bar{d}\bar{g}_L^\uparrow$	v_{15}	Q_0q_1	\bar{v}_L^\uparrow
v_3	Q_0Q_2	dr_R^\downarrow	v_7	Q_0Q_2	$u\bar{b}_R^\downarrow$	v_{11}	Q_0Q_2	$\bar{d}\bar{g}_R^\downarrow$	v_{15}	Q_0Q_2	\bar{v}_R^\downarrow
v_3	q_1Q_2	dr_R^\uparrow	v_7	q_1Q_2	$u\bar{b}_R^\uparrow$	v_{11}	q_1Q_2	$\bar{d}\bar{g}_R^\uparrow$	v_{15}	q_1Q_2	\bar{v}_R^\uparrow
v_3	Q_0Q_3	$\bar{u}r_R^\uparrow$	v_7	Q_0Q_3	$\bar{d}b_R^\uparrow$	v_{11}	Q_0Q_3	$u\bar{g}_R^\uparrow$	v_{15}	Q_0Q_3	\bar{e}_R^\uparrow
v_3	q_1Q_3	$\bar{u}r_R^\downarrow$	v_7	q_1Q_3	$\bar{d}b_R^\downarrow$	v_{11}	q_1Q_3	$u\bar{g}_R^\downarrow$	v_{15}	q_1Q_3	\bar{e}_R^\downarrow
v_3	Q_2Q_3	$\bar{u}r_L^\downarrow$	v_7	q_2Q_3	$\bar{d}b_L^\downarrow$	v_{11}	Q_2Q_3	$u\bar{g}_L^\downarrow$	v_{15}	q_2Q_3	\bar{e}_L^\downarrow
v_3	$Q_0q_1Q_2Q_3$	$\bar{u}r_L^\uparrow$	v_7	$Q_0q_1q_2Q_3$	$\bar{d}b_L^\uparrow$	v_{11}	$Q_0q_1Q_2q_3$	$u\bar{g}_L^\uparrow$	v_{15}	$Q_0q_1q_2q_3$	\bar{e}_L^\uparrow
v_4	1	dr_R^\downarrow	v_8	1	$u\bar{b}_R^\downarrow$	v_{12}	1	$\bar{d}\bar{g}_R^\downarrow$	v_{16}	1	\bar{v}_R^\downarrow
v_4	q_0q_1	dr_R^\uparrow	v_8	q_0q_1	$u\bar{b}_R^\uparrow$	v_{12}	q_0q_1	$\bar{d}\bar{g}_R^\uparrow$	v_{16}	q_0q_1	\bar{v}_R^\uparrow
v_4	q_0Q_2	dr_L^\downarrow	v_8	q_0Q_2	$u\bar{b}_L^\downarrow$	v_{12}	q_0Q_2	$\bar{d}\bar{g}_L^\downarrow$	v_{16}	q_0Q_2	\bar{v}_L^\downarrow
v_4	q_1Q_2	dr_L^\uparrow	v_8	q_1Q_2	$u\bar{b}_L^\uparrow$	v_{12}	q_1Q_2	$\bar{d}\bar{g}_L^\uparrow$	v_{16}	q_1Q_2	\bar{v}_L^\uparrow
v_4	q_0Q_3	$\bar{u}r_L^\downarrow$	v_8	q_0Q_3	$\bar{d}b_L^\downarrow$	v_{12}	q_0Q_3	$u\bar{g}_L^\downarrow$	v_{16}	q_0Q_3	\bar{e}_L^\downarrow
v_4	q_1Q_3	$\bar{u}r_L^\uparrow$	v_8	q_1Q_3	$\bar{d}b_L^\uparrow$	v_{12}	q_1Q_3	$u\bar{g}_L^\uparrow$	v_{16}	q_1Q_3	\bar{e}_L^\uparrow
v_4	Q_2Q_3	$\bar{u}r_R^\downarrow$	v_8	q_2Q_3	$\bar{d}b_R^\downarrow$	v_{12}	Q_2Q_3	$u\bar{g}_R^\downarrow$	v_{16}	q_2Q_3	\bar{e}_R^\downarrow
v_4	$q_0q_1Q_2Q_3$	$\bar{u}r_R^\uparrow$	v_8	$q_0q_1Q_2Q_3$	$\bar{d}b_R^\uparrow$	v_{12}	$q_0q_1Q_2q_3$	$u\bar{g}_R^\uparrow$	v_{16}	$q_0q_1Q_2q_3$	\bar{e}_R^\uparrow

TABLE I. Spinor tableaux for first 16 vacuum idempotents of our Witt basis for $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$.

V.A.5. Triality Automorphism

In companion work preceding this paper Jason Blood [51] establishes an S_3 automorphism of $\mathbb{B}\ell_8$ which we may borrow whole cloth for our T4G model.

There could be later distinct interpretations however, so this is not all a done deal. Blood is using a fibre bundle ontology, whereas T4G uses a pure 4D spacetime + wormholes topology. These morally ought to be distinct theories and morally ought to be separated by experiment, though we have not thought up any tests to date — as tantalizing as these possibilities are for “getting closer to the Great One,” in Einstein’s parlance.

One thing Jason does is identify the copy of the first Standard Model (SM) generation in the first 16 vacua as a light-sector and dark-sector, meaning interacting and non-interacting (or visible and invisible). We are agnostic on this interpretation, but in Jason’s conception it seems perfectly good.

This means his S_3 automorphism (aka. Triality permutation) does provide for genuinely three fermion gen-

erations of the LR-symmetric Standard Model, with this extra \mathbb{Z}_2 doubling structure.

The pure algebra of course is agnostic to our ontological interpretations. Thus to avoid senseless reproduction we quote here at length Blood’s relevant section:

“This already produces the full Standard Model particle content (together with its dark counterpart) for a single family. The algebra, however, contains an additional discrete symmetry: the three complex fiber [sic.] directions ($j = 1, 2, 3$) may be cyclically permuted without changing the defining anti-commutation rules or the Hermitian fiber metric. This permutation symmetry generates three inequivalent embeddings of the same spacetime subalgebra, and therefore three inequivalent identifications of particle states within the ideals. We interpret these three embeddings as the three observed SM generations.

“Importantly, the slide symmetry acts

only on the fiber indices 1, 2, 3. It leaves the light/dark splitting idempotent (built from the fiber pseudoscalar I) and the spacetime base manifold unchanged. Hence each generation automatically comes with both a light and dark copy, while all gauge fields remain common across generations.”

We have checked another version of triality by permuting the (123)) indices on the $C\ell_3$ subalgebra of

$$\{e_i, f_i\}, \quad i \in 1, 2, 3.$$

generating the 2nd and 3rd Witt bases from the corresponding γ_μ . This goes as follows, we have the first Witt basis, $\{q_i, Q_i\}$. Then perform a permutation of the $C\ell_6$, for Gen-II: (12)(23)(31), or in full,

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_4 - e_1), & A_0 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_4 + e_1) \\ a_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(-e_2 - ie_3), & A_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_2 - ie_3) \\ a_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_4 - f_1), & A_2 &= (f_4 + f_1) \\ a_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(-f_2 - if_3), & A_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_2 - if_3) \end{aligned}$$

and the third generation from the permutation, Gen-III: (13)(21)(32), explicitly via,

$$\begin{aligned} b_0 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_4 - e_2), & B_0 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_4 + e_2) \\ b_1 &= (-e_3 - ie_1), & B_1 &= \frac{1}{2}(e_3 - ie_1) \\ b_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_4 - f_2), & B_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_4 + f_2) \\ b_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(-f_3 - if_1), & B_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(f_3 - if_1) \end{aligned}$$

This also appears to yield two new independent sets of 16 vacuum idempotents, hence overall, like Jason, we have three families of fermions again.

A simple check for independence by comparing the Clifford blade structure shows the three sets of 16 vacua are independent, and when we visualize as a large table showing the $(+, -, i)$ coefficients of the basis blades in a Welsh–Hadamard ordering, again it seems clear we have distinct vacuum idempotents [53].

Gresnigt has communicated [54] that there is probably not one unique “physical” S_3 automorphism.

Whether one claims this S_3 automorphism is a deformation of fibre bundle Planck structure or wormhole topology Planck structure is, to our estimation, today almost moot, given today we have no clear probes of Planck scale topology available other than quantum computer qubit operations. In our T4G view, condensed matter physics analogues could be useful too, but are unlikely to shed much light on actual Planck scale minimal topology, due to the T4G topology requiring the ER-bridges collapse if energetically perturbed (the Friedman topological censorship conjecture [20, 55, 56]).

* * *

If we embed sedenions inside $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$ we can get another S_3 automorphism, this is described by Gresnigt and Gourlay

[12, 57]. Also yielding three generations of vacuum idempotents, hence three families of SM fermions.

Note that this would still stand in principle were the spinor monomials in the left Ideals not algebraically independent, because the vacuum idempotent independence suffices. This is because the spinors are always acting on-the-left on the vacua (at least in what we might say is the standard $C\ell$ quantum mechanics formalism).

We have not yet investigated whether these two versions of Triality are equivalent. This is a difficult puzzle due to the different way Gresnigt *et al* treat $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ (unitary gauge transforms on-the-right) compared to J. Blood ($\mathfrak{su}(2)$) unitary on-the-left, and $\mathfrak{su}(3)$ on-the-right).

In summary, there appear to be more than one way to generate the S_3 triality automorphism in the algebra. Our opinion is that short of downstream measurable consequences these kaleidoscopes of triality are mathematical artefacts, and there might be a physical spacetime topology basis for resolving which “reflection” of triality is *the* physical one, if it ever matters (it might not). The unresolved puzzle would be whether the kaleidoscopes of triality is a true pathology redundancy, inconsequential degeneracy, or “only a kaleidoscope”, or whether this kaleidoscope we refer to is itself a mirage.

(In our view similar remarks might apply to Jason’s light/dark duality — is it physically consequential, or a mirage, or an artefact? Could “quantum mechanics” (i.e., entanglement ontology) be found within this structure?)

V.A.6. Yukawa Couplings and Gravity

We have not done any new work on the origins of the Yukawa couplings. However, the coupling does become more natural and “geometric” in the $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$ model. Jason Blood is again the source of beginning of understanding the Yukawa components of the Standard Model [51]. The basic idea is that fermion masses involve an odd grade clifford multivector operator which flips chirality.

Most of this, including the Higgs field, is associated with the vacuum idempotent structure, which is of further interest when we consider Turok & Boyle’s work [15] on the 36 dimension zero scalars which are needed in the LR-symmetric Standard Model (which is Jason’s model) in order to cure the Weyl and vacuum energy anomalies. Some masses appear to be computable by including these 36 dim=0 Bogoliubov scalars [19].

As one last pertinent comment here, let us mention that were the extra copy of the SM in these $\mathbb{C}\ell_8$ algebras “real” in any sense, contributing to scattering amplitudes, this will completely break the aforementioned conformal and energy anomaly cancellations!

The Bogoliubov scalars are not propagating modes, and so are pure vacuum transformations, and are not to be found in the $C\ell_8$ spinor Ideals.

V.A.7. Motivating Cl_{12} exploration?

We mentioned the ribbon braid preon or helon model before. The preon structure was found by Gresnigt [13] in a combination of Cl_4 and Cl_6 .

This suggests a possible tripartite wormhole topology lurking in some sectors of the Standard Model symmetry transforms. If so, then according to our prior naïve philosophy, we might want to triple the STA, not just double.

This can motivate $Cl_{9,1}$ as the minimal requirements, assuming the Lorentzian structure is roughly in common for the whole 4-geon. That would amount to a quasi strong localization assumption. Next we might consider going up to the conformal algebras in a sequence,

$$Cl_{9,1} \rightarrow Cl_{9+1,1+1} \rightarrow Cl_{9+3,3+3}$$

the last being in case we think all three wormhole substructures need separate independent conformal transforms. Then finally repeat all this with our last suspect for a SM transform, some sort of wormhole duality, for which we would complexify these algebras.

This does seem almost ridiculous, and we must too not forget Bott periodicity

$$Cl_{p+8,q} \cong Cl_{p+4,q+4}.$$

So if we did ever decide to motivate, say, Cl_{16} then we should find we need only $Cl_{12,4} \cong Cl_{8,8}$. So... quartite wormhole topology? It will probably never exercise us because the previous Cl_8 seems sufficient.

* * *

In a more mathematico-philosophical vein, we can suggest conceptual reasons why triality occurs in the physical Standard Model. Normally one might naïvely associate triality with reflections, and in $Cl_{6,1}$ or Cl_7 we have 7 such generators. Half of G_2 . One of these is parity, $T_1 = -e_0\phi e_0$ inversion, which we associate with 3-space, since our $e_0 \equiv \gamma_0$ is timelike. The other six are thus associated with spacetime reflections. However, when the abstract 6-dimensional space is reduced to physically 3-dimensions, by identifying two wormhole ends as the “carriers” of two sets of spacetime basis frames, as in the T4G conception of quantum mechanics (§-II.B) then it becomes possible to conceptually imagine that triality is related to bipartite symmetry between wormhole ends. These symmetries need not be static topology, and could be dynamical when conceived of in *physical* terms, but in any case, the vague conceptual idea is that we have a bipartite splitting, so that 6 reflections reduce to only 3 of physical relevance. The vague idea behind this being that the elementary particle structure is itself bipartite — meaning composed of wormhole structure of some variety.

We do not have any more than these speculative remarks as theoretical breadcrumbs for accounting for why

Nature seems to split G_2 , and why the particle content of higher dimensional exceptional Lie groups may not be observable. The additional particles predicted by E_8 theory could of course just be super massive, hence not yet observed, but our T4G model would find it hard to accommodate them, since it is not yet known how to reach the Lie algebra \mathfrak{e}_8 from just 4D spacetime algebra.

VI. THE HIGGS AND THE GRAVITON

We have come across perhaps three or four seemingly distinct approaches to the Higgs mechanism. In the CPT-LR-Symmetric Standard Model approach of Turok & Boyle [25], the Higgs is not fundamental, and is possibly composed via condensation dynamics from 36 dimension zero Bogoliubov scalars. These fields enter the augmented SM Lagrangian via fourth derivatives (quadratic second derivatives). This is much like exploration of fourth derivatives of the Riemann curvature in augmented GR which have been tentatively explored by John Nash [58].

Jason Blood has yet another take on the Higgs [51, see Sec. 6].

According to Bogoliubov *et al* [44] (and Turok & Boyle), these dim=0 scalars have no propagating modes. There is a modelling option involved: whether to (i) remove negative energy states but permit ghosts ((negative probability currents), or (ii) permit ghosts and remove the negative energy states, then perform a GSO-like projection to remove the ghost states, and they opt for the latter.

The result is no new particles, but instead a cure for the vacuum energy. This is highly appealing of course, more especially since coupled with curing the Trace and Weyl anomalies, they arrive at a sharp prediction of exactly 3 generations of fermions. This is the tree level anomaly cancellation of a 4D supersymmetric theory, where the ratio of bosons to fermions to scalars is 1::4::6. (12 bosons, 48 fermions, 36 scalars which get doubled.)

In recent work by Miller *et al* [19] extending [15], the 36 dimension zero scalars have been shown to provide a natural electroweak symmetry breaking, and an account for masses in the Standard Model Lagrangian for massless fermions via a non-minimal coupling to these dim=0 scalars, via the vierbein of GR.

Normally the Einstein Principle of Equivalence (EEP) is explained by *minimal coupling* and position + rotation gauge invariance in GR, so one might worry the foundations of GR are undermined here, but the non-minimal coupling is only observable via the elementary particle masses in just the manner Miller *et al* describe (see also [59]). So is a highly quantum effect. Moreover, without the non-minimal coupling the spinorial matter has no intrinsic mass, and so the tail wags the dog so-to-speak, and the classical foundations of GR are secure.

* * *

In Clifford algebra a Higgs has also been “found” naturally, for example Trayling & Baylis [4] use Cl_7 to construct a one-family Standard Model, and find that their higher dimensional components of the Dirac currents provides a, “Lorentz-invariant vector space [which] is then a carrier space for the set of exterior gauge transformations and affords a natural inclusion of the minimal Higgs field.” In other words, the Higgs field arises simply as a *coupling to the higher-dimensional vector components of the current*.

* * *

In our T4G model, there are no “higher dimensions” *per se*, only additional degrees of freedom in Clifford basis due to wormhole topology, so we can reinterpret these results in a manner that comes closer to Turok & Boyle. Although speculative, we propose that the spacetime vacuum structure has modes that couple wormhole ends, which are inducing the Higgs mechanism. The higher dimensional couplings are, in our view, something like second order effects on the Planck scale. We do not yet have a clear idea of what this means in a 4D gauged GR context [60] but it could be related to wormhole bipartite topology symmetry (at this stage, those are “mere words” with no formal substance).

All told, the 36 dim=0 Bogoliubov scalars seem to fit perfectly with T4G theory, and can be considered ‘pure vacuum’, and much along the same lines as Nash’s tentative ideas [58] can be probably considered ‘pure *spacetime* vacuum’.

VI.A. No graviton?

As we have already remarked, there is no need for a topological graviton in T4G theory, so the graviton should in fact not appear in the Clifford algebra for the Standard Model. The way we say this in colloquial terms is that *gravity is already quantized*, and we should not try to re-quantize gravity, since that would be redundant and invite pathologies.

But having stated this view, gravity will still have quantum effects in T4G theory beyond the Standard Model layer, because the spacetime vacuum is presumably highly entangled (wormholes are ubiquitous). What this implies for proposed experiments to probe gravitationally induced entanglement or spin witnesses for quantum gravity is beyond our scope of inquiry. We would just guess that some quantum effects should be discernable, but would not necessarily require a topological graviton for their explanation.

Gravity is perfectly well described in T4G theory by GR and gravity waves. At the Planck scale the Standard Model topology should become dominant except for the extremes like the classical level singularities in black hole interiors or firewalls (whichever) and the Big Bang.

As further support for T4G we can again appeal to anomaly cancellation: to cancel Weyl and vacuum

anomalies there simply must *not* be any fundamental graviton, at least not in the Standard Model (see [19]). Thus if proposed experiments for “witnessing quantum gravity” prove successful, we would expect there to be an explanation that does not imply a spin=2 topological geon, but rather vacuum entanglement effects that do not involve propagating spin=2 quanta. There is, of course, nothing wrong in “constructing” a composite graviton that does propagate, as is the case for the Bogoliubov scalars composing a non-fundamental Higgs. Just as we do “see” the Higgs at 125 GeV, so we should see a massless but composite graviton have some quantum effects, such as in gravitational wave entanglement phenomena, and gravitational two-slit interference. Given entanglement is discrete and monogamous these effects should be very subtle and hard to detect.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

VII.A. From Six to Three

Suppose our result of an S_3 triality automorphism of the Cl_8 model in § V.A, yielding three independent sets of 16 spinor ideals holds, then is there a natural explanation for why we get 2×3 Standard Model vacua, rather than just 3?

There are at least two or three motivations for answering this question outside T4G theory, and one obvious motive from within.

Within T4G theory we would expect the spinor transformations to be the same either end of the wormholes, so provided the 4-geon wormhole structure is simple, there is probably a type of generalize reflection symmetry, namely shifting what we identify as “the fermion” from one end of a wormhole to another. Through the other end it might not be the same SM charge, but that’s neither here nor there, it would still be an apparent doubling of the SM without a physical doubling, because this view is just a reinterpretation of the Cl_8 algebra.

Black hole mirrors: The results of Turok, Boyle & Tzanavaris [61], have suggested a black hole really does form a complete void in spacetime, and the boundary is a mirror boundary, where anti-particles for matter not only mirror in-falling annihilate, but locally mirror them, thus annihilating into radiation, which just propagates up the boundary until Hawking evaporation whittles away the void. This suggest our cosmos is two-sheeted somehow.

The wild idea is that rather than the entire spacetime manifold being two-sheeted, it really only needs to be locally mirror-like, and the black hole horizons are places we might be seeing the effects thereof. It is not hard to imagine how this could relate to a doubling of the Standard Model algebra, given in T4G theory the spinors are just encoding spacetime transformation instructions.

CPT Symmetric Big Bang: The other result from Turok & Boyle [62] suggests the cosmological arrow of time arises from a similar two-sheeted universe picture.

While this seems more like a genuinely global doubling, it might not be, since the manifestation only needs to be at the conformally symmetric Big Bang, which is now considered a CPT mirror boundary. Since it is still singular in the non-pathological components of the spacetime metric, it is a highly local mirror really, and so the T4G model could be sufficient to provide the relevant real geometry and topology.

Dark sector: The third external support is the light/dark sector duality see e.g., [63, 64]. This is the interpretation chosen by Jason Blood [51].

In our T4G framework we take a different view of dark matter, namely that of Turok & Boyle, where the right-handed neutrino’s are the dark matter galaxy halo, and the doubling of the SM algebra can correspond to “going through the wormhole” in T4G, that is, the other side of a 4-geon wormhole is “invisible” to the experiment, a measurement process need only see one end of the 4-geon. This is also, in our opinion, the natural basis for Unruh–Hawking radiation (or more generally horizon radiation) and hence logically the elementary particle basis for QFT.

* * *

The other possibility is that our calculations of independent vacuum idempotents is flawed, and there are only three independent fermion generations after all. While this would wrap a nice bow on the $\mathcal{C}\ell_8$ Standard Model, it would be the less interesting resolution.

Another possibility is that T4G is wrong, and we really do live in a universe with ontological fibre bundles of some variety. This seems to be Blood’s view [51, see sec.8], and in Blood’s theory there is an entire *light* sector and an entire *dark* sector (meaning the metaphors for interacting and non-interacting fermions). Having not fully understood this theory we cannot dismiss this explanation either.

VII.B. Wild Speculations

It should be clear that T4G is not a revolutionary nor remarkable theory, or proto-theory. However, it does invite more wild speculations.

One is that we can possibly tame quantum gravity in the early universe. When we consider the early universe, going back to radiation domination, eventually in that regime particles lose mass and the dynamics become conformal and CPT invariant. This permits the Big Bang singularity to be “mild” and a mere mirror boundary. Because this regime is scale invariant for all forces except gravity the particles cannot see the singularity (to use a manner of speech as a substitute for the mathematics of a conformal Big Bang boundary).

Universal time goes to zero, but the “stuff of Nature”, the particles, in this regime are only sensitive to conformal time, so the particles never see the boundary, due to conformal invariance. Mathematically the theorist can

describe the boundary using a conformal transform, that “stretches” out the singularity. The QFT is then analytic. The problem remains for gravity, but if exact CPT is imposed the only gravity modes that survive are analytic. Thus the Big Bang seems to almost be tamed.

What is a residual problem is that putative ‘quantum gravity’ is not a known theory and yet should dominate at the boundary. So no one can really say what should occur.

We have a wild idea that perhaps CPT holds right back to conformal $\tau = 0$ which is backed by T4G theory. According to T4G theory quantum mechanics arises from entanglement structure, for which traversable wormholes at the Planck scale are necessary. But in the ultrahigh temperatures of the early universe wormhole structure should not persist for any longer than Planck time scales, due to the enormous radiation density, which will collapse any wormholes. This is because of topological censorship — which is really just the fact that in spacetime a violation of positive or null or weak energy conditions is necessary for wormhole throat stability. The idea then is that wormholes effectively cannot exist in any meaningful sense in the early universe, and so quantum mechanics cannot be effective. Or, at least, quantum mechanics gets smoothly “turned off” as we approach the Big Bang CPT boundary.

We prose this with some trepidation, given that almost all mainstream and non-mainstream cosmology thought today would argue quantum mechanics becomes more, not less, extreme at the Big Bang. This is a prejudice, it presumes there is a proper quantum theory of gravity. T4G is already a quantum theory, and the quantization of gravity is the quantization of spacetime, and that is the Standard Model structure. The topological 4-geon structure of the Standard Model — for which we include the vacuum — *is* quantum gravity, already. Quantum Gravity is nothing else.

We have, for now, just one other wild idea, but which nicely ties together a few threads from above, so will be a good place to finish. This is to connect our tentative interpretation of the wormhole structure as an actual spacetime tensor structure, not just a convenience for analyticity. The argument is in two parts as follows.

Barandes [35] shows it is possible to reformulate all of quantum theory (including QFT) without talking about mysterious “*probability amplitudes*.” His framework of Indivisible Stochastic QM (ISQM) reproduces all of orthodox QM with no mention of the amplitudes. Instead, he has unistochastic matrix elements, which are in his framework clearly not *probabilities*. They are entries in a non-Markov transition matrix. Generically many entries will be negative numbers. The strictly positive non-Markov transition matrix squares the unistochastic entries,

$$\Gamma_{ij}(t) = |U_{ij}|^2$$

the crucial bit of physics is that while the unitary numbers U_{ij} which (more or less) are the solutions to the

Schrödinger or Dirac equations of motion (for an elementary system) satisfy smooth divisible transitions,

$$U(t) = U(t \leftarrow t_0)U(t_0) \quad (\text{Divisible})$$

while the physical transition matrix does not, in general,

$$\Gamma(t) \neq \Gamma(t \leftarrow t_0)\Gamma(t_0) \quad (\text{Indivisible}).$$

In a pattern which should be thoroughly familiar to gauge theory practitioners and general relativists, the failure of Γ to be divisible is identifiable as the interference terms in Schrödinger or Dirac time evolution.

T4G accepts Barandes’ ISQM, but not just because T4G is compatible or agnostic, rather because T4G regards the wormhole structure in planckian spacetime as the source or “cause” of entanglement, and hence in the ISQM framework the “cause” of single-particle interference. However, the entanglement and interference in ISQM are in the structure of the generically \mathbb{C} -valued unistochastic entries, not the non-Markov transition matrices *per se*. See [35, sec. D, Eq. (76)]. This supports our contention that the complexification of the Cl_8 algebra is the hallmark of entanglement and interference. In bare bones T4G (without any SM particle phenomenology) the only possible cause of entanglement (and interference) is the conjectured Planck scale 4-geon wormhole

topology. In other words, we really had no choice but to complexify and double the spacetime algebra.

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